

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP4

Grid planning and operation strategies

Deliverable D4.5

Monitoring & control automation architecture for Hybrid AC/DC Distribution

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List of Abbreviations

AHP	Analytical Hierarchy Process
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DG	Distributed Generators
DMS	Distribution Management System
DMU	DC Measurement Unit
DSO	Distribution System Operator
FLISR	Fault Location Isolation and Service Restoration
GSA	Global Sensitivity Analysis
GTNET	Gigabit Transceiver Network
HV	High Voltage
LSA	Local Sensitivity Analysis
MAS	Multi-Agent System
MCDA	Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis
MCS	Monte Carlo Simulation
MIQP	Mixed-Integer Quadratic Programming
MISOCP	Mixed-Integer Second-Order Cone Programming
MV	Medium Voltage
NC	Normally Closed
NIS	Negative Ideal Solution
NO	Normally Open
OPF	Optimal Power Flow
PDF	Probability Density Function
PIS	Positive Ideal Solution
PV	Photovoltaic
PWM	Pulse-Width Modulation
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RTDS	Real Time Digital Simulator
RTUs	Remote Terminal Units
QoI	Quantity of Interest
SA	Sensitivity Analysis
SE	State Estimation
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
SR	Service Restoration
TOPSIS	Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
VSC	Voltage Source Converters
WLS	Weighted Least-Squares
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The AC-DC distribution networks require dedicated approaches for the monitoring and optimal management. System operators have to upgrade their Distribution Management System (DMS) in order to account for the new DC-based components and their optimal utilisation. In particular, the presence of AC-DC and DC converters, as well as DC based loads and generators, introduces new challenges and possibilities for the optimal automation of distribution systems. This document presents the energy services that have been developed within the Task T4.5 "Monitoring and control automation architecture for Hybrid DC/AC Distribution Network" of HYPERRIDE project.

To upgrade the protection strategies of system operator in presence of DC sub-networks, the Service Restoration (SR) algorithm dedicated for AC-DC distribution networks have been proposed. This algorithm, independent by grid topology and network parameters, categorises the priorities of disconnected nodes to form the set of candidate solutions for the network reconfiguration. Each candidate solution is tested with an Optimal Power Flow (OPF) that, in addition to the real time measurements, accounts for the forecasts of load and generation. Multiple criteria are pursued and prioritised according to user preferences. Multiple test cases demonstrates its applicability in different scenarios as well as test grids, providing noticeable information about the contribution of DC sub-networks in case of fault occurrences.

To perform accurate and advanced monitoring of AC-DC distribution networks, the Weighted Least-Squares (WLS) State Estimation (SE) is deployed and tested. This algorithm is based on a two-steps SE that relies on separated SE for each sub-network (AC and DC) and the exchange of converter power flow measurements. Additionally, the role of measurement on converters modulation index has been accounted and investigated. The algorithm has been integrated in a real time simulation setup and the included test results shows the performances of the algorithm in the different grid conditions and with various measurements sets.

Another approach to state estimation is the use of machine learning algorithms as predictors of relevant quantities at different locations in the grid from both sparse and redundant measurements, in the form of a generalised view on state estimation. Two machine learning algorithms are employed to answer questions related to observability and ideal measurement unit placement in a hybrid AC-DC grid. Machine learning models are very fast predictors, making them ideally suited for real-time (control) applications. However, they are sensitive to noisy or unexpected data. Therefore methods were investigated to make the models more robust and to find the most suitable algorithm for different application cases.

The deployed energy services constitute key elements for the HYPERRIDE ICT platform, integrating additional software components for the management of data communication protocols, measurements and commands in accordance with cybersecurity aspects, data storages and user interfaces. The proposed energy algorithm will constitute the baseline, providing specific knowledge about peculiar monitoring and operation requirements, for the deployment and tests in HYPERRIDE pilots.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document presents the energy services, as software components, developed according to the activities in Task T4.5 "Monitoring and control automation architecture for Hybrid DC/AC Distribution Network" of Work Package 4 "Grid planning and operation strategies" in the HYPERRIDE project.

The applicability and benefits of DC technology for power distribution systems have been analysed in the Work Package (WP) 2 "Requirements, use cases and specifications". Recent research achievements have allowed to reduce the construction material of power electronics devices and, consequently, their production costs; these advancements favour the continuous increase of power electronics based components as AC-DC and DC-DC converters, which constitute the keys for the uptake of DC-based distribution grids. Multiple research and industrial pilots have been presented in the WP2 deliverables; the pilots include the replacement of existing AC lines with DC ones or the construction of dedicated DC-based feeders. In each case, the DC sub-network will be integrated into the AC distribution systems to form a hybrid AC-DC distribution electrical network.

Besides the electrical components, which constitute the hardware of the DC sub-networks, such as DC circuit breakers, DC sensors, DC Measurement Unit (DMU) and AC-DC or DC-DC converters, specific control strategies and dedicated algorithms are necessary. In fact, the existing energy services, currently deployed in the software platforms of Distribution System Operator (DSO) for the management of electrical networks, are not suitable for the integration of DC sub-networks and cannot exploit their full potential or risk to be compromised: new solutions must account for the system level control among different Distributed Energy Resources (DER) and AC-DC converters, synchronising their operations, and integrate advanced monitoring solutions for AC-DC distribution networks.

Specifically, the energy services deployed in Task T4.5 (and presented in this document) are SR and SE; for SE two algorithms are presented: a WLS based AC-DC estimator and a machine learnt robust one, including the ideal measurement unit placement. These algorithms provide significant insights into the advanced automated control of AC-DC distribution networks and allow them to optimize their operations.

The deployed services are interconnected with the other WP and tasks of HYPERRIDE project. In particular, the energy services, developed according to the outcomes of WP2, are integrated with the HYPERRIDE ICT platform developed in WP5 "Open and secure ICT for modular resilient optimized hybrid grid": the data models that constitute the inputs and outputs of energy services are aligned with the data layer developed in Task 5.2 "Scalable and decentralized hybrid AC/DC oriented sensing and monitoring layer" and, together with the other key platform components (Orion Context Broker, databases and data visualisation, etc.) will constitute the baseline for the Task 5.6 "Open ICT platform adaptation and evolution". The energy services, together with the ICT HYPERRIDE platform, will be then tested in the pilots of HYPERRIDE projects, as in WP7 "German pilot" in the dedicated Task 7.4 "Validation of the automation energy services".

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 1 provides information about the report content. The developed energy services are presented in the following chapters, in particular: Section 2 describes the SR algorithm and its validation tests as published in the scientific paper (Dognini, Ginocchi, De Din, Ponci, & Monti, 2023), the WLS based SE is discussed in Section 3, whereas the machine learnt robust SE, together with the ideal measurement unit placement, is found at Section 4. The deliverable is concluded in Section 5.

2 Service Restoration

2.1 Introduction

The decentralization of energy management in AC distribution grids, together with the growth of electricity demand (e.g., in the mobility sector and temperature control of buildings), toughens criticalities related to power quality, protection and control of power flow; the upgrade of networks with power electronics components, based on DC technology, could mitigate these issues (Nejabatkhah & Li, 2015), (Coffey, Timmers, Li, Wu, & Egea-Álvarez, 2021). Particularly, several research activities propose the deployment of point-to-point or multi-terminal DC lines, linking DC-based generators and loads via DC-DC converters, to interconnect AC distribution grids (Priebe, Wehbring, & Moser, 2018; Gelani, Dastgeer, Nasir, Khan, & Guerrero, 2021; Montoya, Gil-González, Hernández, Giral-Ramírez, & Medina-Quesada, 2020). The decentralization of energy management in AC distribution grids, together with the growth of electricity demand (e.g., in the mobility sector and temperature control of buildings), toughens criticalities related to power quality, protection and control of power flow; the upgrade of networks with power electronics components, based on DC technology, could mitigate these issues (Nejabatkhah & Li, 2015), (Coffey et al., 2021). Particularly, several research activities propose the deployment of point-to-point or multi-terminal DC lines, linking DC-based generators and loads via DC-DC converters, to interconnect AC distribution grids (Priebe et al., 2018; Gelani et al., 2021; Montoya et al., 2020). To achieve this grid configuration, (Zhang et al., 2019) and (Bach, Schlegel, & Westermann, 2020) analyze the conversion of AC lines to DC lines for Medium Voltage (MV) networks, enhancing the power distribution in different network conditions. The energy management of AC-DC distribution grids relies on the control of power converters, enabling the optimization of power transfer among AC and DC sub-networks as an additional controllability feature (Grainger & De Doncker, 2021).

In deploying AC-DC distribution grids, further characterizations are needed for the protection schemes. Protection systems aim at enhancing the reliability of distribution grids, by minimizing the duration of electricity interruption and the affected geographical area (Eggleston, Zuur, & Mancarella, 2021). The DMS of modern distribution grids deploys automated self-healing functionalities commonly referred to as Fault Location Isolation and Service Restoration (FLISR), which encompasses: the accurate determination of fault position, the operation of switching devices to isolate the minimum fault area and, then, the network reconfiguration to re-energize the restorable buses (located downstream the fault area) (Jabr & Džafić, 2022), (Zidan et al., 2017).

In this chapter, the SR aspect of FLISR, for AC-DC networks, is addressed and a dedicated algorithm, developed in the context of the HYPERRIDE project, is presented. Being applied to AC-DC distribution grids, the control of the converters, to optimize the power transfer among AC and DC sub-networks, has to be included in the SR process. Multiple research works have presented OPF approaches for AC-DC grids, to determine operational setpoints of converters and Distributed Generators (DG). In (Ahmed & Salama, 2019) and (Zhuo, Zhang, Kang, Dong, & Liu, 2018) the mathematical models of AC-DC grids are expressed as OPF constraints and linearized; in (Yang, Zhong, Bose, Xia, & Kang, 2018), additionally, the detailed characterization of operating limits and losses for AC-DC converter station is included. The work presented in (Qi et al., 2018) proposes a decentralized approach, sub-dividing the optimization problem in AC sub-networks, DC sub-networks and AC-DC converters levels. In these studies, the proposed methods do not consider the SR use case, whereby network portions are electrically disconnected and the operating strategies have to be accordingly adapted; nonetheless, the

referred OPF formulations are integrated in the SR algorithm, applied to each reconfiguration solution.

Several works have addressed the design of SR algorithms for AC-DC grids. Prioritization of de-energized buses is of importance to compute the different reconfiguration topologies that involve the operation of Normally Open (NO) and Normally Closed (NC) switches. In this context, e.g., (Li, Xu, He, Zhang, & Liu, 2019) proposes a graph theory approach to optimize the power transfer among AC and DC sub-networks in SR, though being designed uniquely for meshed HV grids; in fact, MV distribution networks are operated uniquely with radial feeders (in order to simplify the protection system), making this proposed method not applicable. The algorithm proposed in (S. Jiang, Liu, Gao, Zhao, & Wang, 2019) determines the available restoration paths with a genetic algorithm, but the DC lines only interconnect AC-DC converters without modelling loads and DG; this aspect is particularly relevant since the future AC-DC distribution networks aim at directly connecting DC generation and DC consumption in the same sub-network, reducing the conversion stages. Ref. (Zhang et al., 2023) presents a SR method based on Mixed-Integer Second-Order Cone Programming (MISOCP) in which the de-energized loads are ranked according to their criticality and iteratively reconnected, although the opening of NC switches is not included in the restoration topologies hence limiting the set of candidate solutions.

In determining the candidate solutions for SR, the prioritization of the de-energized loads is of high importance, particularly in the case each bus cannot be reconnected. In (Xu, Liu, Schneider, Tuffner, & Ton, 2018) and (Bajwa et al., 2021) the SR computes the priority indices of every bus with respect to the hosted critical infrastructures (e.g. emergency facilities or communication networks); however, this approach is expanded in the present work by computing the indices of bus groups and the nominal power of hosted DG and loads.

Moreover, the design of a suitable SR algorithm shall consider the time period between the fault clearance and the final network reparation; hence the applicability of the solution has to be verified, in addition to the actual time instant with the measured data, also in a specific time horizon by considering the forecast values as loads and generation profiles. Refs. (Gangwar, Mallick, Chakrabarti, & Singh, 2020) and (H. Jiang, Ding, & Zhang, 2017) present network reconfiguration algorithms that consider the short-term power forecasts in determining the switches to be operated, but this aspect is not extended among the objective criteria of the SR problem.

The deployment of SR with multiple criteria allows to enhance the algorithm performance and consider the different DSO objectives. Ref. (Lou et al., 2019) proposes a Mixed-Integer Quadratic Programming (MIQP) model to reconfigure the AC-DC distribution networks, by optimizing the combination of lost load, minimum DG curtailments and minimum network loss; whereas in (Cai et al., 2022) a hierarchical coordinated optimization solution method is applied, which considers the minimum active power loss and AC bus voltage offset of the distribution network as the optimization goals. These literature works deploy weighting factors in the optimization functions to combine the different criteria, introducing inconsistency and losing control over each optimization goal. On the contrary, the algorithm proposed in this paper resorts to the Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) approach, in that it provides the user with the possibility to flexibly select specific SR criteria and define their priorities. Within MCDA, as the first step, the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) allows to compute the priorities of every criteria starting from a pair-wise comparison according to DSO objectives (Saaty, 1990). Then, as the second step, the Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) technique is applied, in which the weights of criteria are combined with the set of candidate solutions. The goal is to compute the most optimal candidate solution, which is nearest to the positive ideal solution and farthest from the negative ideal solution (Tzeng &

Huang, 2011).

To understand the implications that the relationships between diverse restoration criteria, i.e., the inputs to the MCDA approach, might have on its outcomes, SA comes into the fore. Traditional SA approaches mainly belong to the family of Local Sensitivity Analysis (LSA) (Edwards & Newman, 1986), which is based on individual perturbations of the uncertain weights to analyze their effect on the outcome of the decision analysis process, hereafter referred to as Quantity of Interest (QoI). Graphical tools such as tornado diagrams, rainbow diagrams and strategy-region diagrams are usually adopted to visualize the LSA results (Howard, 1988). A review of SA techniques for multi-objective decision-making is provided in (Insua & French, 1991) and a comparison of a selected number of SA techniques (one- and two-way SA and regression analysis) is reported in (Bauer Jr., Parnell, & Meyers, 1999). However, LSA techniques— although being by far the dominant ones in the power system field, as shown in (Ginocchi, Ponci, & Monti, 2021)— capture the effect of small perturbations on the QoI, hence being suitable to study only small changes in the close vicinity of the inputs operational/nominal values, unless the model is shown to have a linear behavior. As a consequence, LSA might be insufficiently informative and poorly performing in those situations whereby the studied model is characterized by large uncertainties of the inputs, nonlinearities or potentially even unknown degree of linearity (e.g., in the case of black-box models). To overcome these downsides, Global Sensitivity Analysis (GSA) is recommended, as it is able to explore (at least conceptually) the overall variability range of the inputs hence providing a more complete picture of the model sensitivity behavior. Different GSA techniques are available in the literature (Ginocchi et al., 2021): in this work, the choice is to adopt variance-based SA— which, to the best of authors' knowledge, has not been previously applied to study the sensitivity of MCDA approaches for SR purposes—, due to its easiness of interpretation, its ability to comprehensively account for all the uncertainty sources and its independence from any prior assumption on the model properties.

The work carried out in the Task T4.5 of HYPERRIDE project, with respect to the SR algorithm, has led to the following:

- The development of an SR algorithm for the computation of network reconfiguration solutions, including the opening of NC switches and accounting for the calculated priorities of the de-energized buses. The algorithm is specifically designed for AC-DC distribution networks, integrating a convexified OPF that enhances the SR performance by optimizing the operational control of DG and AC-DC converters.
- The implementation of the MCDA technique to select, among feasible candidates, the near-optimal SR solution. The adopted criteria consist of the minimization of network power losses, the use of telecontrolled switches for the reconfiguration and the applicability of proposed network topologies in the long term (in the time period beyond the fault occurrence).
- The quantitative analysis of the impact of the MCDA comparison parameters on the SR process via variance-based SA. By applying such GSA method, the effect of the subjective judgements on the computation of the near-optimal solution in the SR process is quantitatively retrieved to support the algorithm implementation (e.g., identifying which MCDA comparison parameters mostly affect the decision of the SR solution), ultimately enabling an informed decision-making process under uncertainty.

2.1.1 Structure of the chapter

This chapter is structured as follows: Section 2.2 formulates the SR problem and describes

the MCDA and OPF techniques; Section 2.3 describes the different steps of the proposed SR algorithm; Section 2.4 describes the GSA methodology and the adopted variance-based SA technique; Section 2.5 presents and discusses the results obtained by running the proposed SR algorithm on three selected case studies; Section 2.6 provides the final conclusion.

2.2 Formulation of Service Restoration Problem

The occurrence of faults in electrical networks, such as short-circuits or series faults, requires the prompt intervention of the protection system, which detects the event and determines its location. The coordination of the switches to be operated (circuit breakers, reclosers, load break switches and disconnectors), in accordance with the selectivity plan, allows the minimization of the isolated fault area by opening the nearest switches upstream and downstream of the fault location. The MV grids are normally operated with radial configuration and different feeders are interconnected by NO tie-switches. Hence the buses belonging to the faulty feeder but located downstream the fault area are indicated here as “restorable”, i.e., although being de-energized, they can be reconnected by closing specific tie-switches. The goal of SR is to re-energize the maximum number of restorable buses according to specific criteria while ensuring the secure operation of the network. The topology yielded by the reconfiguration process is temporary, lasting several hours (on average, between 2 and 4 hours), and precedes the crew intervention to repair the faulty line (Pretico, Marinopoulos, & Vitiello, 2021).

Figure 1: Overview of the SR algorithm.

The SR algorithm proposed in the HYPERRIDE project starts as soon as the fault area is isolated by the open upstream and downstream switches; the flowchart in Fig. 1 depicts the main steps, which are described hereafter.

- a) Identify the restorable buses and, consequently, the alternative sets of switches commands (as candidate solutions) for the network reconfiguration.
- b) For each candidate solution:
 - Verify the feasibility according to grid security constraints.
 - Deploy the OPF to compute setpoints for DG and AC-DC converters.

- Quantify the criteria using MCDA technique.
- c) Determine the near-optimal candidate solution to be implemented, by comparing the MCDA outcomes.
 - d) In the case no candidate solution is feasible, repeat the process by excluding the least critical buses from the re-energization.

Each step of the SR process is hereafter described and their mathematical formulations are presented.

2.2.1 Identification of restorable buses and computation of candidate solutions

As first step, the SR algorithm uses the information of the tripped switches to identify the de-energized buses outside the fault area. Depending upon the position of controllable switches, multiple power sources can re-energize the restorable buses.

The graph theory is applied to model the distribution network: each bus and line of the electrical grid corresponds to vertex c and edge e , respectively. Each bus has attributes associated with the possible presence of an AC-DC converter station or High Voltage (HV) connection (consisting of HV/MV primary substation); the attributes of each edge specify the presence of a switch and, in case, the switch status (open or close) as well as the tripping condition (due to a fault, encompassing the fault area). Afterwards, the graph without edges corresponding to open switches (NO and tripped switches) is built; for each bus of the network, the connectivity, as a finite sequence of edges, toward each power source (HV/MV substation, also through AC-DC converter) is inspected: if a bus is not connected to any power source, it is identified as disconnected and added to the set C , which is the array of disconnected buses. Then, a new graph with edges corresponding to NO and NC switches but without tripped switches is built; for each disconnected bus, the connectivity toward each power source is verified: in the case a bus is connected to, at least, one power source, the former is identified as restorable; the array of restorable buses is indicated by C_r . Within C_r , some restorable buses are directly connected among them without interposed switches; since the SR algorithm includes the possibility to open the NC switches within the de-energized area, the buses not interconnected by any switch correspond to a “bus group”. All the buses of a bus group will be re-energized simultaneously. The array C_r^g contains sub-arrays $C_r^{g,b}$ that indicate the buses in the bus groups (with $b = 1, 2, \dots, n_g$ and n_g being the number of bus groups).

The sample 10-bus grid in Fig. 2 represents a radial AC grid with a DC sub-network; black and white squares indicate the NC and NO switches, respectively. A fault at bus 2 causes the tripping of switches S1 and S2 and, consequently, the de-energization of buses 3, 4 and 5. Since buses 3 and 4 are not interconnected by switches, they constitute a unique bus group. Hence the following bus arrays are obtained:

$$C = [2, 3, 4, 5]$$

$$C_r = [3, 4, 5]$$

$$C_r^g = [[3, 4], [5]]$$

If the computed SR solution causes the power flow to violate the network security constraints (e.g. voltage or ampacity limits), an SR solution shall be implemented that re-energizes only

Figure 2: Sample 10-bus AC-DC distribution grid.

part of disconnected buses. Hence it is important to classify the disconnected bus groups, in order to prioritize the re-energization of the “most important” buses.

2.2.2 Prioritization of bus groups with MCDA

The MCDA technique allows to mathematically determine the candidate solution, among multiple ones, that satisfies at best the objective criteria. In this specific application, MCDA is used to determine the order of priorities for bus groups considering the pre-determined criteria. To this scope, the index α is introduced and assigned by the DSO to each bus: the greater α , the higher the criticality of the infrastructure. The criteria considered by MCDA, based on which each bus group b is evaluated, are:

1. The highest criticality value for the bus group, indicated as α_{max} . For the bus group $C_r^{g,b}$, it writes:

$$\alpha_{max}^b = \max \{ \alpha_c, \forall c \in C_r^{g,b} \} \quad (1)$$

2. The total generated power P_{gen} in the bus group, as sum of nominal power for each DG, if present, connected to the buses. For the bus group $C_r^{g,b}$, it writes:

$$P_{gen}^b = \sum_{c \in C_r^{g,b}} (P_{gen,c}) \quad (2)$$

3. The total absorbed power P_{load} in the bus group, as the sum of nominal power for each load connected to the buses. For the bus group $C_r^{g,b}$, it writes:

$$P_{load}^b = \sum_{c \in C_r^{g,b}} (P_{load,c}) \quad (3)$$

The first step of the MCDA is the application of the AHP (Saaty, 1990). Pair-wise comparisons among the criteria (α_{max} , P_{gen} , P_{load}) are carried out and the symmetric comparison matrix Γ

(with dimensions $d \times d$, with d being the number of criteria) is obtained:

$$\mathbf{\Gamma} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & W_{\alpha_{max} P_{gen}} & W_{\alpha_{max} P_{load}} \\ \frac{1}{W_{\alpha_{max} P_{gen}}} & 1 & W_{P_{gen} P_{load}} \\ \frac{1}{W_{\alpha_{max} P_{load}}} & \frac{1}{W_{P_{gen} P_{load}}} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Each element w in $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ indicates the pre-assigned comparison parameter between the two criteria indicated by the subscripts (α_{max} , P_{gen} or P_{load}), in the AHP scale, ranging discretely from 1/9 (i.e., the attribute of the first subscript is extremely irrelevant with respect to the second one) to 9 (i.e., the attribute of the first subscript is extremely important with respect to the second one). In the work developed in HYPERRIDE, the highest importance is assigned to α_{max} criteria; moreover, for the same criticality index, the restoration of buses hosting DG is considered more important than the restoration of loads. The implemented values of comparison parameters are:

$$W_{\alpha_{max} P_{gen}} = 4 \quad W_{\alpha_{max} P_{load}} = 9 \quad W_{P_{gen} P_{load}} = 4$$

The weights of the criteria are the elements of the eigenvector \mathbf{v} , according to:

$$(\mathbf{\Gamma} - \lambda_{max} \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{v} = 0 \quad (5)$$

where λ_{max} is the respective largest eigenvalue of matrix $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ and \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix with dimension $d \times d$.

Afterwards, the TOPSIS (as part of MCDA) is applied (Tzeng & Huang, 2011). The performance ratings matrix \mathbf{D} is first created, having o rows as the number of alternatives and d columns as number of criteria:

$$\mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1d} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2d} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{o1} & a_{o2} & \dots & a_{od} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

In this application, o and d correspond to the number of bus groups and the number of MCDA criteria, respectively; each element of \mathbf{D} indicates the value of the criteria (α_{max} , P_{gen} or P_{load}) for the specific alternative (i.e., the bus group).

Then, the performance ratings are normalized and multiplied by the weights of criteria (as elements of the eigenvector \mathbf{v}) computed with AHP:

$$y_{ij} = \frac{a_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^o a_{ij}^2} v_j \quad i = 1, \dots, o; j = 1, \dots, d; \quad (7)$$

As next step, the Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) and Negative Ideal Solution (NIS) are calculated:

$$PIS = \left\{ \left(\max_i y_{ij} \mid j \in J_1 \right), \left(\min_i y_{ij} \mid j \in J_2 \right) \mid i = 1, \dots, o \right\} = \{y_1^+, y_2^+, \dots, y_d^+\} \quad (8)$$

$$NIS = \left\{ \left(\min_i y_{ij} \mid j \in J_1 \right), \left(\max_i y_{ij} \mid j \in J_2 \right) \mid i = 1, \dots, o \right\} = \{y_1^-, y_2^-, \dots, y_d^-\} \quad (9)$$

where J_1 is the set of benefit criteria (i.e. the criteria that aim at being maximized) and J_2 is the set of cost criteria (i.e., the criteria that aim at being minimized), respectively. For the prioritization of bus groups, every criteria belongs to J_1 .

As next step, the Euclidean distance of each alternative from PIS (S_i^+) and NIS (S_i^-) is computed:

$$S_i^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^d (y_{ij} - y_j^+)^2} \quad i = 1, \dots, o \quad (10)$$

$$S_i^- = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^d (y_{ij} - y_j^-)^2} \quad i = 1, \dots, o \quad (11)$$

Finally, the relative closeness of each alternative i to the ideal solution Q_i^+ is computed:

$$Q_i^+ = \frac{S_i^+}{(S_i^+ + S_i^-)} \quad (12)$$

In particular, the larger Q_i^+ , the better the performance of alternative i . The bus groups belonging to C_r^g are then sorted in descending order based on Q_i^+ and constitute, as sub-arrays, the array of prioritized bus groups indicated as C_r^{g*} .

It is noteworthy that the above-described MCDA technique is also used in a successive stage of the SR process (described in Section 2.2.5) to determine the most optimal network reconfiguration topology to be implemented.

2.2.3 Computation of candidate solutions for network reconfiguration

Starting from the restorable buses C_r to be re-energized, the SR candidate solutions are computed in the form of network reconfiguration topologies. By considering the graph of the network without the tripped switches, the most suitable path—if it exists—between each bus of C_r and every HV/MV substation (also through AC-DC converters) is computed by implementing the Dijkstra's algorithm (Sudhakar, Vadivoo, Slochanal, & Ravichandran, 2004): given two buses c_1 and c_2 in a graph G , it determines the path G'_{c_1, c_2} to connect c_1 and c_2 by minimizing a specific attribute of the edges. In the implemented application, the attribute to be minimized is the impedance of the lines, in order to minimize the power losses of the SR solution. The computed paths guarantee the radiality of the network and include, among the edges, the NO switches whose closure allows to re-energize the restorable buses. Multiple occurrences of the same NO switches are discarded and the array S_{NO} is computed: it contains as many as s_{NO} sub-arrays S_{NO}^v , which indicate combinations of NO switches to be operated in order to re-energize all the restorable buses:

$$S_{NO} = \left[\bigcup_{v=1}^{s_{NO}} [S_{NO}^v] \right] \quad (13)$$

Moreover, the SR algorithm considers the opening of NC switches among the bus groups within the de-energized area. The computation of the shortest paths among each restorable bus and every HV/MV substation with Dijkstra's algorithm is repeated; however in this case the edges related to the opened NC switches are excluded from the graph. It is worth mentioning that, since the simultaneous opening of adjoining NC switches (i.e., among adjoining bus groups) could cause the isolation of restorable buses located in the middle, the location of NC switches leads to the definition of two categories:

- The “non-adjoining NC switches”, which are simultaneously opened (being them connected to different bus groups) and determine unique SR candidate solutions.

- The “adjoining NC switches”, which are alternatively opened and determine different SR candidate solutions.

The array S_{NO}^{NC} is then formulated, which contains s_{NC}^{NO} sub-arrays indicated by $S_{NO}^{NC,z}$. Each $S_{NO}^{NC,z}$ sub-array is constituted by:

1. As initial elements, indicated by $S^{NC,z}$, the combination of non-adjoining NC switches to be closed.
2. As successive elements, indicated by $S_{NO}^{*,z}$, the combinations of NO switches to be closed. The order of NO switches reflects the order of prioritized bus groups in C_r^{g*} .

The array S_{NO}^{NC} assumes the following general formulation:

$$S_{NO}^{NC} = \left[\bigcup_{z=1}^{s_{NC}^{NO}} [S_{NO}^{NC,z}] \right] = \left[\bigcup_{z=1}^{s_{NC}^{NO}} [S^{NC,z}, S_{NO}^{*,z}] \right] \quad (14)$$

Each $S_{NO}^{NC,z}$ sub-array constitutes a different SR candidate solution to be further evaluated. It is worth mentioning that, due to the opening of NC switches, the bus groups that are not encompassed by tie switches (as NO switches) cannot be re-energized and are hence removed from the array of restorable buses C_r .

Considering the sample grid of Fig. 2 and assuming the prioritization of the bus groups (with MCDA technique) that leads to:

$$C_r^{g*} = [[5], [3, 4]]$$

it is, then, obtained:

$$S_{NO} = [[S4], [S6]]$$

$$S_{NO}^{NC} = [[S3, S4, S6]]$$

It is noteworthy that only one candidate solution as sub-array $S_{NO}^{NC,z}$ is present in S_{NO}^{NC} as the opening of NC switch $S3$ requires the closure of both NO switches $S4$ and $S6$ to re-energize every restorable bus. The candidate solutions of the SR process are constituted by the combinations of NO switches in each sub-array S_{NO}^y of S_{NO} and, moreover, by the combinations of NC and NO switches in each sub-array $S_{NO}^{NC,z}$ of S_{NO}^{NC} . Each specific candidate solution is indicated by K_x , with $K = S_{NO} \cup S_{NO}^{NC}$ being the whole set of candidate solutions.

2.2.4 Optimal Power Flow for the Candidate Solutions

Each candidate solution (calculated as described in Section 2.2.3) indicates the NO switches to be closed and, eventually, the NC switches to be opened, determining the network topology that constitutes the input for the OPF computation. The deployment of OPF has two goals: to verify the applicability of the candidate solution with respect to the operational and security limits and, moreover, to optimize the power injections of DG and AC-DC converters (related to the power exchange between AC and DC sub-networks).

The model of AC-DC converters is developed according to Voltage Source Converters (VSC) technology and is represented in Fig. 3. In general, the DC sub-networks deploy a multi-terminal configuration (i.e., more than two electrically connected AC-DC converters) and in the operational strategy one AC-DC converter acts as DC slack bus, according to which the voltage of its corresponding bus n is set to 1 p.u., while the other converters set the active

Figure 3: Model of AC-DC converter station.

power setpoints (Yang et al., 2018); in the deployed operational strategy, the droop control of DC voltage is not included. Moreover, considering the model in Fig. 3 and the directions of the power flows (e.g. a positive value of P_C^{DC} indicates that the power is flowing from the AC-DC converter to the DC grid), the power losses of the converter station P_C^{loss} are defined as:

$$P_C^{loss} = -P_C^{AC} - P_C^{DC} \quad (15)$$

with P_C^{AC} and P_C^{DC} being the active powers injected in the AC and DC sides, respectively, of the AC-DC converter. It is worth to highlight that, since power flows from one side (AC or DC) to the other, P_C^{AC} and P_C^{DC} have always opposite signs (one entering the converter and the other leaving it) and, additionally, P_C^{loss} cannot assume a negative value (i.e., power cannot be generated by the AC-DC converter itself but just transferred from one side to the other). For the considered VSC station, P_C^{loss} aggregates the losses of each station component: transformer, filter, phase reactor, and converter. The power losses of the transformer, filter and phase reactor are related to the core losses and harmonic currents. The power losses of the AC-DC converter include both switching and conduction losses (Bahrami, Therrien, Wong, & Jatskevich, 2017). The power losses of the entire AC-DC converter station are approximated with a quadratic function of the phase current $I_{C,m}$ at bus $m \in N_C$ (with N_C as a set of converter buses) and the parameters a_c , b_c and c_c :

$$P_{C,m}^{loss} = a_c + b_c |I_{C,m}| + c_c |I_{C,m}|^2 \quad (16)$$

where a_c , b_c , and c_c are positive coefficients representing the constant or no-load losses (e.g., filter losses, transformer core losses), the linear losses (e.g., switching), and the quadratic losses (e.g., transformer, phase reactor copper losses, and conduction losses), respectively (Bahrami et al., 2017).

The OPF is formulated based on the branch flow model defined in (Farivar & Low, 2013), which describes a convex relaxation procedure for solving the OPF (normally nonconvex). The resulting objective function corresponds to the minimization of network power losses, indicated by P_{tot}^{loss} in (17), and it is defined as:

$$P_{tot}^{loss} = \sum_{i,j \in N_{AC}} r_{ij} l_{ij} + \sum_{p,q \in N_{DC}} r_{pq} l_{pq} + \sum_{m \in N_C} P_{C,m}^{loss} \quad (17)$$

where $r_{ij} l_{ij}$ represents the real power losses in the AC grid, composed by the real part of the line impedance, r_{ij} , and the square of the branch current, l_{ij} , for all $i, j \in N_{AC}$, with N_{AC} being the AC buses. The term $r_{pq} l_{pq}$ represents the power losses in the DC grid, where r_{pq} is the line resistance and l_{pq} is the square of the branch current for all $p, q \in N_{DC}$, with N_{DC} being the DC buses.

The constraints for AC-DC distribution grids are:

- Power balance constraints at AC buses $i \in N_{AC}$:

$$P_{gen,i}^{AC} + P_{C,i}^{AC} - P_{load,i}^{AC} = - \sum_{j \in N_{up}} (\mathcal{P}_{ji}^{AC} - r_{ji} I_{ji}) + \sum_{k \in N_{down}} \mathcal{P}_{ik}^{AC} \quad (18)$$

$$Q_{gen,i}^{AC} + Q_{C,i}^{AC} - Q_{load,i}^{AC} = - \sum_{j \in N_{up}} (Q_{ji}^{AC} - x_{ji} I_{ji}) + \sum_{k \in N_{down}} Q_{ik}^{AC} \quad (19)$$

where \mathcal{P}_{ji}^{AC} and Q_{ji}^{AC} represent the active and reactive power between the node i and the set of upstream neighboring nodes N_{up} , whereas the term x_{ji} is the imaginary part of the corresponding line impedance. The elements \mathcal{P}_{ki} and Q_{ki} represent the active and reactive power between the node i and the set of downstream neighbouring nodes N_{down} . $P_{gen,i}^{AC}$ and $Q_{gen,i}^{AC}$ indicate the active and reactive power injected by generators connected to node i , $P_{C,i}^{AC}$ and $Q_{C,i}^{AC}$ indicate the active and reactive power injected by AC-DC converter connected to node i (equal to zero if the AC-DC converter is not present in node i) whereas $P_{load,i}^{AC}$ and $Q_{load,i}^{AC}$ indicate the active and reactive power absorbed by loads connected to node i .

- Power balance constraints at DC buses N_{DC} :

$$P_{gen,p}^{DC} + P_{C,p}^{DC} - P_{load,p}^{DC} = - \sum_{q \in N_{up}} (\mathcal{P}_{qp}^{DC} - r_{qp} I_{qp}) + \sum_{r \in N_{down}} \mathcal{P}_{pr}^{DC} \quad (20)$$

where, based on (15), $P_{C,p}^{DC}$ is substituted with:

$$P_{C,p}^{DC} = -P_{C,i}^{AC} - P_{C,m}^{loss} \quad (21)$$

where \mathcal{P}_{qp}^{DC} represents the active power between the node p and the set of upstream neighboring nodes N_{up} , whereas \mathcal{P}_{pr} represents the active power between the node p and the set of downstream neighboring nodes N_{down} . $P_{gen,p}^{DC}$ indicates the active power injected by generators connected to node p , $P_{C,p}^{DC}$ indicates the active power injected by AC-DC converter connected to node p (equal to zero if the AC-DC converter is not present in node p) whereas $P_{load,p}^{DC}$ indicates the active power absorbed by loads connected to node p .

- Power losses constraints at AC-DC converter; to comply with the convex OPF, the equation (16) is relaxed to the inequality:

$$P_{C,m}^{loss} \geq a_c + b_c |I_{C,m}| + c_c |I_{C,m}|^2 \quad (22)$$

The set of constraints characterizing the AC-DC interface of the electrical system, namely (15), (18), (19), (20) and (22), are described in Figure 4, which shows how the interface is correctly modeled by the constraints.

- AC voltage calculation at AC buses $i \in N_{AC}$ with respect to node $j \in N_{up}^{AC}$:

$$v_i = v_j - 2(r_{ji} \mathcal{P}_{ji}^{AC} + x_{ji} Q_{ji}^{AC}) + (r_{ji}^2 + x_{ji}^2) I_{ji} \quad (23)$$

where v is the square of the node voltage.

- DC voltage calculation at DC buses $p \in N_{DC}$ with respect to node $q \in N_{up}^{DC}$:

$$v_p = v_q - 2 r_{qp} \mathcal{P}_{qp}^{DC} + (r_{qp})^2 I_{qp} \quad (24)$$

where v is the square of the node voltage.

Figure 4: Interface at the AC-DC converter.

- AC current at AC-DC converter buses N_C ($m \in N_C$):

$$(I_{C,m})^2 = \frac{(P_{C,m}^{AC})^2 + (Q_{C,m}^{AC})^2}{V_m^2} \quad (25)$$

Given the quadratic inequality, this constraint is nonconvex. Therefore, following (Farivar & Low, 2013), the constraint is relaxed to inequality:

$$(I_{C,m})^2 \geq \frac{(P_{C,m}^{AC})^2 + (Q_{C,m}^{AC})^2}{v_m} \quad (26)$$

where v_m is the square of the node voltage.

- AC current at AC buses $i \in N_{AC}$ with respect to node $j \in N_{up}^{AC}$. From (Farivar & Low, 2013) the following relaxed constrained is obtained:

$$I_{ji}^{AC} \geq \frac{(P_{ji}^{AC})^2 + (Q_{ji}^{AC})^2}{v_i} \quad (27)$$

- DC current at DC buses $p \in N_{DC}$ with respect to node $p \in N_{up}^{DC}$. From (Farivar & Low, 2013) the following relaxed constrained is obtained:

$$I_{qp}^{AC} \geq \frac{(P_{qp}^{DC})^2}{v_p} \quad (28)$$

- Voltage coupling between AC and DC converter sides (m and n buses, respectively, as in Fig. 3), considering the range of Pulse-Width Modulation (PWM) converter modulation index $m_{C,m}$ as $[0,1]$, taken from (Grainger & De Doncker, 2021):

$$v_m \leq \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\sqrt{2}} \right)^2 v_n \quad (29)$$

This constraint is not applied to the DC slack converter, for which $v_n = \left(\frac{2\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}} \right)^2$

- AC current limit for AC-DC converters:

$$I_{C,m} \leq I_{C,m}^{\max} \quad (30)$$

- Reactive power limits for AC-DC converters (i.e., maximum values of absorption and injection), considering $m_{B,m}$ as the converter constraint factor and $S_{C,m}^{nom}$ as the nominal apparent power of the converter. The lower limit is taken from (Bahrami et al., 2017):

$$-m_{B,m}S_{C,m}^{nom} \leq Q_{C,m}^{AC} \quad (31)$$

whereas the upper limit, as described in (Yang et al., 2018), is represented by the upper limit on the bus voltage, which corresponds to the combination of (26) and (30).

- Power limits for AC and DC generators (including DG), considering the $\cos\phi_{gen,i}$ as operational power factor of the generator i and $Q_{gen,i}^{AC,max} = P_{gen,i}^{AC,max} \cos\phi_{gen,i}$:

$$P_{gen,i}^{AC,min} \leq P_{gen,i}^{AC} \leq P_{gen,i}^{AC,max} \quad (32)$$

$$-Q_{gen,i}^{AC,max} \leq Q_{gen,i}^{AC} \leq Q_{gen,i}^{AC,max} \quad (33)$$

$$P_{gen,p}^{DC,min} \leq P_{gen,p}^{DC} \leq P_{gen,p}^{DC,max} \quad (34)$$

For DG, the upper limits $P_{gen,i}^{AC,max}$, $Q_{gen,i}^{AC,max}$ and $P_{gen,p}^{DC,max}$ vary according to the available or forecasted power in the time frame of OPF execution.

- Power limits for AC and DC lines:

$$\left(P_{ji}^{AC}\right)^2 + \left(Q_{ji}^{AC}\right)^2 \leq S_{ji}^{AC,max} \quad (35)$$

$$\left(P_{qp}^{DC}\right)^2 \leq P_{qp}^{DC,max} \quad (36)$$

where $S_{ij}^{AC,max}$ represents the maximum apparent power of the line between buses i and j , whereas $P_{qp}^{DC,max}$ represents the maximum active power of the line between buses p and q .

- Voltage limits for AC and DC buses:

$$\left(V_i^{min}\right)^2 \leq v_i \leq \left(V_i^{max}\right)^2 \quad (37)$$

$$\left(V_p^{min}\right)^2 \leq v_p \leq \left(V_p^{max}\right)^2 \quad (38)$$

The conic relaxation of the OPF would normally require the solution to satisfy the angle recovery conditions (Farivar & Low, 2013). However, the radial characteristic of the AC side of the AC-DC distribution grid always guarantees the condition to be satisfied. The fulfilment of the angle recovery conditions for meshed grids is normally not trivial and could lead to an infeasible solution for the OPF. In a meshed DC network this problem does not occur, since the angles are always zero. Consequently the conic relaxation of the OPF always produces an optimal solution.

The OPF calculations are based on network parameters and real-time measurements. Additionally, the forecast values, as explained in Section 2.2.5, are integrated to inspect the applicability of the proposed SR candidate solutions in the successive hours.

2.2.5 Selection of restoration solution with MCDA

Each candidate solution for which the OPF problem does not provide a solution (i.e., the operational and security limits are not respected) is discarded. The MCDA technique explained in 2.2.2 (to prioritize the disconnected bus groups) is applied in the SR algorithm to quantify the validity of each feasible candidate solution and select the near-optimal one.

The categories of criteria considered for the MCDA are detailed hereafter.

1. The parameter β corresponds to the number of switches, both NC and NO included in the considered candidate solution (as switches to be operated), that owns the telecontrolled feature (i.e., can be operated from the DSO control centre). Indicating a switch as S and a telecontrolled switch as S_t , for the candidate solution K_x the parameter β corresponds to:

$$\beta_x = \text{count} \{S \equiv S_t, \forall S \in K_x\} \quad (39)$$

The telecontrolled feature is worth to be considered: a telecontrolled switch, in fact, does not require the time-consuming intervention of DSO crew at the device location and reduces the duration of SR condition (Willis, Northcote-Green, & Wilson, 2017).

2. The power losses P of the AC-DC network represents the value of the objective function of the OPF, from (17), applied to the candidate solution:

$$P_x = P_{tot}^{loss} \mid K_x \quad (40)$$

3. The applicability of the candidate solution is verified with OPF using real-time data. Considering that the reparation of the permanent fault by the DSO crew can last multiple hours, it is worth to verify the applicability of the SR solution being implemented (e.g., for voltage, power and ampacity constraints) also in the successive hours. Hence the OPF is repeated by considering the power forecasts with time frames of 15 minutes (according to the typical time resolution of power forecasts). To this scope, four η parameters are introduced, i.e., η_1 , η_2 , η_3 and η_4 , covering a total verification period of four hours. Each of them records the number of applicable solutions for four 15-minute-frames (i.e., each η parameter accounts for one hour) and hence can assume discrete values from 0 to 4. Should no OPF solution for a specific time frame be found, the process is interrupted and the successive η parameters are set as zero. In formal terms, considering t as the actual time frame, the four η parameters write:

$$\eta_1 = \text{count} \left\{ \exists P_{tot}^{loss, t+x} \mid \exists P_{tot}^{loss, t+x-1} \right\} \quad x = 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad (41)$$

$$\eta_2 = \text{count} \left\{ \exists P_{tot}^{loss, t+x} \mid \exists P_{tot}^{loss, t+x-1} \right\} \quad x = 5, 6, 7, 8 \quad (42)$$

$$\eta_3 = \text{count} \left\{ \exists P_{tot}^{loss, t+x} \mid \exists P_{tot}^{loss, t+x-1} \right\} \quad x = 9, 10, 11, 12 \quad (43)$$

$$\eta_4 = \text{count} \left\{ \exists P_{tot}^{loss, t+x} \mid \exists P_{tot}^{loss, t+x-1} \right\} \quad x = 13, 14, 15, 16 \quad (44)$$

Considering the six above-described criteria (β , P , η_1 , η_2 , η_3 and η_4) the symmetric comparison

matrix Γ of AHP process assumes the following configuration:

$$\Gamma = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & W_{\beta P} & W_{\beta\eta_1} & W_{\beta\eta_2} & W_{\beta\eta_3} & W_{\beta\eta_4} \\ \frac{1}{W_{\beta P}} & 1 & W_{P\eta_1} & W_{P\eta_2} & W_{P\eta_3} & W_{P\eta_4} \\ \frac{1}{W_{\beta\eta_1}} & \frac{1}{W_{P\eta_1}} & 1 & W_{\eta_1\eta_2} & W_{\eta_1\eta_3} & W_{\eta_1\eta_4} \\ \frac{1}{W_{\beta\eta_2}} & \frac{1}{W_{P\eta_2}} & \frac{1}{W_{\eta_1\eta_2}} & 1 & W_{\eta_2\eta_3} & W_{\eta_2\eta_4} \\ \frac{1}{W_{\beta\eta_3}} & \frac{1}{W_{P\eta_3}} & \frac{1}{W_{\eta_1\eta_3}} & \frac{1}{W_{\eta_2\eta_3}} & 1 & W_{\eta_3\eta_4} \\ \frac{1}{W_{\beta\eta_4}} & \frac{1}{W_{P\eta_4}} & \frac{1}{W_{\eta_1\eta_4}} & \frac{1}{W_{\eta_2\eta_4}} & \frac{1}{W_{\eta_3\eta_4}} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (45)$$

Successively, the TOPSIS technique is deployed; the performance ratings matrix \mathbf{D} has, in this application, n rows as the number of alternatives and six columns as the number of criteria. The criteria β , η_1 , η_2 , η_3 and η_4 aim at being maximised and, then, are considered in J_1 as benefit criteria, whereas P is a cost criteria in J_2 as its minimization is sought after. Among the candidate solutions inspected with MCDA process, the one having the larger value of Q_i^+ is elected as the near-optimal to be implemented.

The presented MCDA criteria relate to different aspects of the service restoration: the operational obstacles in modifying the network topology, the efficiency of the computed solution (linked to its power losses and, consequently, to the economical costs) and its reliability in the following hours (while the grid remains faulted). Additional criteria can be easily added in the SR algorithm with limited required effort.

2.3 Description of the implemented Service Restoration algorithm

The different stages of the SR process, specifically described in the previous Sections, are combined together to deploy the SR algorithm. The DMS of the DSO, in which the SR algorithm is implemented, relies on different types of databases for the data that will be processed: static databases contain information regarding the topology and parameters of the network, whereas dynamic databases collect the data measurements and the logical statuses of field devices (Jabr & Džafić, 2022). The proposed SR algorithm is designed as middleware, with the properties of being independent of the grid topology and electrical parameters; it is developed to directly interface the DMS databases and its field implementation require the event-driven communication of fault occurrences from field devices. Both manual and telecontrolled switches can be used (with different impacts in the MCDA); SR switching operations and calculated set-points are sent to the Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition (SCADA) system over the data bus, for which the controllability of AC-DC converters and DG is required.

The flowchart of the implemented SR algorithm is shown in Fig. 5. The algorithm starts when, following a fault occurrence, the circuit breakers trip to interrupt the fault current and, eventually, additional switching devices perform operating sequences (opening and closing) to minimize the number of buses in the fault area. As initial step the algorithm determines the restorable buses C_r and bus groups C_r^b to be reconnected. By means of MCDA, the buses groups are prioritized and the candidate solutions of the SR process are calculated, defining the arrays S_{NO} and S_{NO}^{NC} . The algorithm inspects, with OPF, the feasibility of each candidate solution in a specific group of candidate solutions. If at least one feasible SR solution is found, the near-optimal solution is determined. Otherwise, due to the impossibility to find a solution respecting grid security constraints such as voltage, power and ampacity limits, the successive group of

Figure 5: Flowchart of the service restoration algorithm.

candidate solutions, in hierarchical order, is considered. The hierarchically ordered groups of candidate solutions, from the first one being inspected, are determined according to the following:

1. The re-energization of every restorable bus with NO switches, according to the array S_{NO} . Each sub-array S_{NO}^V corresponds to a different candidate solution.
2. The inclusion of NC switches operation in the network reconfiguration, according to the array S_{NO}^{NC} . Each sub-array $S_{NO}^{NC,z}$ corresponds to a different candidate solution.
3. The SR is applied, according to the OPF feasibility, only to the bus groups having the highest priorities. From each sub-array $S_{NO}^{NC,z}$ the last element is removed (i.e., the NO switch, connected to the bus group with the lowest priority, is not operated) and re-inspected as candidate solution with OPF. The new array is indicated as S_{NO-1}^{NC} .
4. The removal of the last NO switch in each $S_{NO}^{NC,z}$ is repeated and re-inspection with OPF is carried out. If every NO switch is removed in a sub-array $S_{NO}^{NC,z}$, the specific sub-array is discarded from the candidate solutions. The process continues until all NO switches are removed by every sub-arrays, in which case the SR process is interrupted.

Accordingly, the groups of candidate solutions are:

$$S_{NO}, S_{NO}^{NC}, S_{NO-1}^{NC}, S_{NO-2}^{NC}, \dots, S_{NO-h}^{NC}$$

with h being the maximum number of $S_{NO}^{NC,z}$ reductions, as per point 4) of the previous paragraph. By inspecting each group of candidate solutions (from S_{NO} to S_{NO-h}^{NC}), the near-optimal solution, if suitable, is identified with the MCDA technique according to the criteria β , P , η_1 , η_2 , η_3 and η_4 . Consequently, the closing and opening commands are issued via the DMS data bus to the corresponding switching devices (for telecontrolled switches) or as information to the DSO crew (for manual switches); moreover, the controller setpoints, as obtained from the OPF results, are sent to AC-DC converters and DG. The SR process is then concluded.

2.4 Global Sensitivity Analysis for MCDA Assessment

In this work, SA is employed to quantitatively assess the uncertainty of the candidate solutions and apportion it to the variability of the MCDA comparison parameters. As the determination of the near-optimal SR solutions depends on the pair-wise comparison parameters among the MCDA criteria in the AHP matrix Γ , SA is deployed to quantify the influence of the AHP comparison parameters on the SR solutions, ultimately providing precious information under the algorithm implementation viewpoint.

2.4.1 Sensitivity analysis

In this study the general methodology for running global SA is adopted (Ginocchi et al., 2021), whose main steps are briefly summarized here.

1. The analysis goal is defined.
2. The QoI for the analyst is selected according to the goals of the analysis.
3. The uncertainty sources (also referred to as inputs), which might have potential influence on the selected QoI, are identified and the model elements which are not subject to the SA are set at their nominal values.
4. The uncertainty of the considered inputs is characterized in probabilistic terms, e.g., in terms of Probability Density Function (PDF) encapsulating the analyst's degree of knowledge of the inputs variability.
5. The SA method suitable for the problem at hand is selected.
6. The input samples of the N -dimensional Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) are drawn from the space of the plausible input combinations according to specific sampling strategies (e.g., random or quasi-random numbers, etc.).
7. The model response is collected by evaluating the model at the values of inputs combinations specified by each MCS sample.
8. The variability of the QoI is characterized via specific metrics of interest (e.g., mean, variance, etc.).
9. The specific sensitivity measures of the selected SA method are computed to identify the most influential uncertainty sources.
10. Graphical tools are employed to effectively visualize the results.
11. After interpreting the first round of SA results, successive iterations of the whole procedure might be done to explore different scenarios (e.g., to refine the inputs uncertainty, to consider different inputs, etc.).

In Table 1 the specific instantiation of the above-reported SA procedure is described, and the corresponding results are presented in Section 2.5.2.

2.4.2 Variance-based sensitivity analysis

Specifically, variance-based SA— widely acknowledged as the “gold standard” technique for analyzing the effect of different uncertainty sources on a specific QoI (Saltelli et al., 2007)— is

Table 1: Instantiation of the main steps of the SA procedure for the specific problem under study.

Step	Description
1) Define analysis purpose	Evaluate the effect of the variability of MCDA comparison parameters on SR solution
2) Select QoI	Values of Q_i^+ — as per (12)— for each feasible candidate solution
3) Identify model inputs	15 pair-wise comparison parameters in the AHP matrix Γ of (45)
4) Define inputs PDFs	Discrete uniform PDF with support $k \in \{1/9, 1/8, \dots, 1/2, 1, 2, \dots, 9\}$
5) Choose SA method	Variance-based SA
6) Define sample size N	$N = 2000$
7) Collect model response	Run the MCDA for each of the 2000 MCS samples
8) Characterize the QoI variability	Compute mean and standard deviation
9) Compute the Sensitivity Indices	Compute Sobol' sensitivity indices
10) Graphical visualization tools	Box plots and heat maps
11) Iterate the analysis	Fix the most influential comparison parameter and repeat the SA

adopted in this study given its easiness of interpretation, its ability to account for the whole variability range of the considered uncertainty sources and its model-free nature (i.e., not assuming any kind of a priori information about the model such as linearity or monotonicity).

Consider a generic mathematical model of the form:

$$Y = g(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_K) \quad (46)$$

whereby Y is the QoI— assumed scalar for convenience— and X_1, X_2, \dots, X_K are the K model inputs, the latter assumed to be independent random variables with a specific PDF. In the application under study, the QoI Y is Q_i^+ of (12) for each feasible candidate solution and the model inputs X_1, X_2, \dots, X_K are the 15 pair-wise comparison parameters in the AHP matrix Γ of (45). Under the assumption of input independence, variance-based SA aims at decomposing the total variance $Var(Y)$ of the QoI into contributions of individual inputs and combinations thereof, according to (Saltelli & Sobol', 1995):

$$Var(Y) = \sum_i Var_i + \sum_i \sum_{i < j} Var_{ij} + \dots + Var_{ij\dots K} \quad (47)$$

where

$$Var_i = Var_{X_i}(\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i)) \quad (48)$$

$$Var_{ij} = Var_{X_{ij}}(\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim ij}}(Y|X_i, X_j)) - Var_{X_i}(\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i)) - Var_{X_j}(\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim j}}(Y|X_j)) \quad (49)$$

and so on for higher-order terms.

Specifically, the inner operator of (48), i.e., $\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i)$, is the expected value \mathbb{E} of Y taken over $\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}$, i.e., all possible values of the inputs except X_i which is kept fixed, whereas the outside operator Var is the variance taken over all possible values of X_i . Accordingly, the term $Var_{X_i}(\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(Y|X_i))$ describes the variance reduction that would be obtained, on average, if X_i could be fixed at its “true” (albeit unknown) value.

It is usually more convenient to normalise (48), hence leading to the definition of Sobol' sensitivity indices:

$$1 = \sum_i S_i + \sum_i \sum_{i < j} S_{ij} + \dots + S_{ij\dots K} \quad (50)$$

where S_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, K$) are the first order Sobol' indices, which quantify the effect of the uncertainty of each input taken alone, whereas the higher order indices (e.g., S_{ij}) account for possible combined effects among inputs (e.g., among inputs X_i and X_j). If the model is additive, i.e., without interactive effects among inputs, all terms of (50) higher than the first order are zero, yielding $\sum_i^K S_i = 1$. On the other hand, if interactions among inputs are present, $\sum_i^K S_i < 1$ and the quantity $1 - \sum_i^K S_i$ is an indicator of the overall amount of interactions present in the model.

In practice, instead of calculating all the sensitivity indices of (50) higher than the first order ones, the so-called total Sobol' index T_i is computed to capture the overall contribution of the input X_i (Homma & Saltelli, 1996):

$$T_i = \frac{\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(\text{Var}_{X_i}(Y|\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}))}{\text{Var}(Y)} = 1 - \frac{\text{Var}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(\mathbb{E}_{X_i}(Y|\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}))}{\text{Var}(Y)} \quad (51)$$

where $\text{Var}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(\mathbb{E}_{X_i}(Y|\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}))$ represents the variance reduction that would be obtained, on average, if all inputs except X_i could be fixed at their "true" values. On the other hand, the residual variance $\mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}}(\text{Var}_{X_i}(Y|\mathbf{X}_{\sim i}))$ represents the contribution to the QoI variance due to all terms of any order—in the decomposition formula of (50)—that include X_i . Therefore, T_i accounts for the overall contribution of input X_i , including not only its first-order effect, but also all the other (higher-order) effects due to possible interactions with other inputs. For the sake of the example, for a model with $K = 3$ inputs, the total Sobol' index for the input X_i is given by $T_1 = S_1 + S_{12} + S_{13} + S_{123}$. In general, $\sum_i^K T_i \geq 1$. Importantly, the quantity $T_i - S_i$ signals how much the input X_i is involved in interactions with other model inputs: a high value of this quantity highlights a high interactive role of X_i in the model. Moreover, an input having $T_i \approx 0$ can be considered as non-influential and, hence, it can be fixed at any convenient value within its variation range without significantly impacting the outcome.

Notably, the set of all the S_i s together with all the T_i s provides the analyst with an overall and satisfactorily complete picture of the sensitivity behaviour of the model, with higher-order Sobol' indices being selectively computed only if further investigation is needed.

2.5 Results of Case Studies

In this Section, the proposed SR algorithm is deployed on three different distribution networks, i.e., a 20 bus AC-DC grid, the correspondent AC version (to show the comparison due to the absence of the DC sub-network) and a 182 bus AC-DC grid to test the algorithm scalability. The results of selected test cases for these three case studies are presented in Sections 2.5.1, 2.5.3 and 2.5.4, respectively.

The programming language Python v3.8 is used to implement the algorithm and, specifically, the OPF applies the solver IPOPT v3.14 with the package Pyomo v6.4. The software platform is hosted on a 64-bit Windows machine with an i5 - 2.5 GHz processor and 8 GB RAM.

In the MV distribution grids of the case studies, the buses host loads (associated with the categories "residential" or "industrial"), and DG from renewable energy sources (such as wind turbines and Photovoltaic (PV) units). The power absorbed by loads and maximum generated power by DG depend on the representative power profiles (as active power in per-unit scale) that consider the measurement time (with time frames of 15 minutes) in specific days and seasons of the year. In this work, two types of days (week- or weekend-day) and seasons (summer or winter) are considered, originating four scenarios for load and generation profiles: summer-week, summer-weekend, winter-week and winter-weekend. The profiles data, extracted from a

Figure 6: Daily load and generation profiles for: (a) Summer season and week day. (b) Summer season and weekend day. (c) Winter season and week day. (d) Winter season and weekend day.

German historical database, are obtained from representative residential and industrial loads (BDEW, 2022), averaged wind turbines generation in 2020 (Open Power Systems Data, 2022) and PV profiles with variable cloudiness levels created with the tool in (Pau, Angioni, Ponci, & Monti, 2019). The four scenarios of power profiles used in the case studies are shown in Fig. 6. These power profiles are combined with nominal power and power factor for each load and DG to compute the power injections inputs for the OPF, both in the actual time of fault occurrence (as field measurements) and in the successive time frames (as forecasts, to compute the values of criteria η_1 , η_2 , η_3 and η_4).

2.5.1 Modified CIGRE AC-DC network

As first test grid the “CIGRE MV Distribution Network Benchmark” in the European configuration is used and modified by integrating a multi-terminal DC sub-network (CIGRÉ, 2018). The grid, with base power 1 MVA, is represented in Fig. 7; two AC feeders at 20 kV are connected to the HV/MV transformer stations, indicated by SS1 and SS2, and to the multi-terminal DC sub-network at 32.6 kV via the converter stations C1, C2 and C3. According to the standard EN 50160, the voltage limits in (37) and (38) are set at $\pm 10\%$. The NO and NC switches, present only in the AC sub-network, are represented with white and black squares, respectively, and the

Figure 7: Modified CIGRE AC-DC Network.

subscript t indicates the telecontrolled feature. The line parameters as well as nominal power and power factors of loads (as residential or industrial) and DG are obtained from (CIGRÉ, 2018); the wind turbine is present at bus 19, whereas the PV units are located in buses 3, 4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 16, and 18. The parameters of each AC-DC converter station are taken from (Grainger & De Doncker, 2021),(Bahrami et al., 2017) and reported in Table 2. The converter station C1 acts as DC slack bus; this operational configuration has been kept fixed in all the presented tests since the choice of a different converter station does not impact the unfeasibility of a specific candidate solution.

Table 2: Parameters of AC-DC converter stations (in p.u. scale).

a_c	b_c	c_c	$S_{C,m}^{nom}$	$m_{B,m}$
1.10e-2	2.57e-3	2.42e-3	3e0	5e-1
$R_{r,m}$	$X_{r,m}$	B_f	$R_{T,f}$	$X_{T,f}$
2e-4	8e-3	7e-2	5e-4	1.25e-2

The investigated test case considers the occurrence of a fault at bus 3. Accordingly, to accomplish the protection procedures, the upstream switch S1 trips and, to isolate the fault area, the

downstream switches S2 and S3 are open. The array of disconnected buses C is:

$$C = [3, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11]$$

As bus 3 is within the fault area, it cannot be re-energized with the SR process. Hence, it is excluded from the restorable buses, which are:

$$C_r = [7, 8, 9, 10, 11]$$

Considering the presence of NC switches S6 and S7 among the restorable buses, the array of restorable bus groups is:

$$C_r^g = [[7, 8], [9], [10, 11]]$$

The MCDA technique described in Section 2.2.2, with the indicated comparison parameters $W_{\alpha_{\max} P_{\text{gen}}}$, $W_{\alpha_{\max} P_{\text{load}}}$ and $W_{P_{\text{gen}} P_{\text{load}}}$, is deployed. The highest criticality values, combined with the generated and consumed power at each restorable bus group, yield the array of prioritized bus groups C_r^{g*} :

$$C_r^{g*} = [[9], [10, 11], [7, 8]]$$

To re-energize these disconnected buses, the array S_{NO} (with combinations of NO switches) is obtained:

$$S_{NO} = [[S5], [S8], [S9]]$$

The closure of every single switch (S5, S8 or S9) restores every bus in C_r and corresponds to a specific SR candidate solution. The NC switches interconnecting the bus groups are S6 and S7; since the bus groups are adjoining, both S6 and S7 are classified as “adjoining NC switches” and must be alternatively opened. The array S_{NO}^{NC} (with combinations of NO and NC switches) corresponds to:

$$S_{NO}^{NC} = [[S7, S8, S5], [S7, S8, S9], [S6, S5, S8], [S6, S9, S8]]$$

Each sub-array of S_{NO}^{NC} (to be considered in the case no sub-array in S_{NO} is applicable) re-energizes every bus in C_r and corresponds to a different candidate solution. It is worth to mention that the order of NO switches reflects the prioritized bus groups in C_r^{g*} : in the case no sub-array in S_{NO}^{NC} is applicable, the last element of each array (i.e., NO switch) may be removed and only the buses with highest priorities will be re-energized.

In order to deploy the MCDA and determine the near-optimal candidate solution, the AHP comparison parameters are set for the criteria β , P , η_1 , η_2 , η_3 and η_4 , forming the comparison matrix Γ . In the deployed test cases, two sets of AHP comparison parameters are considered, associated with the matrices Γ_1 and Γ_2 whose values are reported in Table 3. The comparison parameters in Γ_1 prioritize the applicability of the candidate solutions in the successive hours (i.e., the criteria associated with η_1 , η_2 , η_3 and η_4), whereas the comparison parameters in Γ_2 prioritize the use of telecontrolled switches (i.e., the criteria associated to β); these aspects are reflected in the values of $w_{\beta\eta_1}$, $w_{\beta\eta_2}$, $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$.

Table 3: AHP comparison parameters for the evaluation of SR candidate.

AHP Set	Values of comparison parameters														
	$w_{\beta P}$	$w_{\beta\eta_1}$	$w_{\beta\eta_2}$	$w_{\beta\eta_3}$	$w_{\beta\eta_4}$	$w_{P\eta_1}$	$w_{P\eta_2}$	$w_{P\eta_3}$	$w_{P\eta_4}$	$w_{\eta_1\eta_2}$	$w_{\eta_1\eta_3}$	$w_{\eta_1\eta_4}$	$w_{\eta_2\eta_3}$	$w_{\eta_2\eta_4}$	$w_{\eta_3\eta_4}$
Γ_1	3	1/5	1/4	1/3	1/2	1/7	1/6	1/5	1/4	3	4	5	3	4	3
Γ_2	5	2	3	4	5	1/6	1/5	1/4	1/3	2	3	4	2	3	4

The SR process is deployed considering the occurrence of the fault at the time frames equal to 15, 30, 45, 60, 75 and 90 for each scenario in Fig. 6 (i.e., summer-week, summer-weekend, winter-week and winter-weekend). Moreover, the tests are carried out considering the absorbed power of loads equal to 100% and 120% of the nominal values. Each scenario is indicated by a label in the form of “X-Y-t”: “X” indicates the season (Summer “S” or Winter “W”), “Y” indicates the day (Week “W” or Weekend “WE”) and “t” represents the 15-minute time frame.

In each test, for each feasible candidate solution, the criteria for the MCDA are computed. The spider plots of Fig. 8 show the values of the six criteria for four selected scenarios, i.e., S-WE-30 and W-W-15 with nominal loads values at 100% and 120%. In these scenarios, the candidate solutions correspond to the NO switches included in S_{NO} : the three candidate solutions are applicable and the opening of NC switches in the de-energized area is not deployed. The different graphs show how the available candidate solutions differ with respect to each considered criteria. For the scenario S-WE-30, in both the loading conditions, the use of comparison parameters Γ_1 or Γ_2 determines the selection of different SR solutions to be implemented.

In every SR test, the relative closeness Q_i^+ for each candidate solution i is computed: the highest value determines the near-optimal SR solution that is implemented. The heat maps in Fig. 9 show the closeness for each inspected scenario with the different configurations of AHP comparison parameters and nominal load values; consequently the SR topology being implemented is directly identified by the candidate solution with the highest Q_i^+ in the specific row. The blue cells without the value indicate the unfeasibility of the corresponding candidate solutions in the specific scenarios; whereas the white cells imply that, in the specific scenarios, the corresponding candidate solutions have not been inspected, because feasible solutions are already identified in groups with higher hierarchical order (as described in Section 2.3). For every test with nominal load values at 100% (panels (a) and (b) in Fig. 9), at least one S_{NO} candidate solution is feasible and, hence, the S_{NO}^{NC} candidate solutions are not inspected. The deployment of Γ_1 or Γ_2 determines different SR solutions in several cases, particularly in the central hours of the day. Whereas, in specific scenarios of nominal load values at 120% (panels (c) and (d) in Fig. 9) no candidate solution with only NO switches is feasible. Specifically, in S-W-45 and W-W-45, among the four candidate solutions of S_{NO}^{NC} , only [S6, S9, S8] is feasible and is implemented, re-energizing each restorable load. In S-WE-45, W-W-75 and W-WE-45 even [S6, S9, S8] is not feasible as result of OPF and, hence, the S_{NO-1}^{NC} candidate solutions are inspected ([S7, S8], [S6, S5] and [S6, S9]): among them, only [S6, S9] is feasible and implemented; as a consequence, the buses 10 and 11 remain de-energized.

The test outcomes show the importance and effectiveness of MCDA technique in computing the SR solution to be implemented, particularly by quantifying the different Q_i^+ values of the available candidate solutions. The determination of the SR solution without the proposed MCDA technique may lead to non-optimal network topologies and operating setpoints, causing worse energy distribution conditions (here, between 0.9% and 99.5% of closeness difference among feasible candidate solutions in the same scenario, in the TOPSIS scale) with respect to the considered criteria.

Fig. 10 shows the active power setpoints for the AC sides of each AC-DC converter, injected at buses 2, 6 and 12 in every tested scenario with nominal loads values at 100% and 120%. The increases of power injected by C2 into the AC sub-network, accompanied by the reduction of power injected by C1 and C3, reflect the scenarios for which the closure of switch S8 corresponds to the candidate solution. In general, the power exchange among AC and DC sub-networks is greater in scenarios with nominal loads values at 120% than in those with 100%, denoting the importance of power converters in regulating the power flows while ensuring the respect of operating limits. The power injected by C2 with nominal loads values at

Figure 8: MCDA criteria of feasible candidate solutions for modified CIGRE AC-DC network in the scenarios: (a) S-WE-30 with nominal load values at 100%. (b) S-WE-30 with nominal load values at 120%. (c) W-W-15 with nominal load values at 100%. (d) W-W-15 with nominal load values at 120%.

100% is greater than the one with nominal loads values at 120% in specific scenarios, i.e., when the candidate solution corresponds to the closure of switch S8 only in the 100% loads condition.

2.5.2 Sensitivity analysis results

The SA methodology described in Table 1 is employed to assess and quantify the impact of the subjective judgements (i.e., the assigned w comparison parameters) on the calculation of the near-optimal solution in the SR process resulting from the utilized MCDA approach. Considering the AHP method presented in Section 2.2.2, the comparison parameters range discretely between 1/9 and 9. Hence, SA is applied by considering comparison parameters

Figure 9: MCDA closeness values for modified CIGRE AC-DC network: (a) Γ_1 comparison parameters and nominal load values at 100%. (b) Γ_2 comparison parameters and nominal load values at 100%. (c) Γ_1 comparison parameters and nominal load values at 120%. (d) Γ_2 comparison parameters and nominal load values at 120%.

Figure 10: Active power setpoints for converters in the near optimal solutions, nominal load values at 100% and 120% (Γ_1 comparison parameters).

over the whole AHP range, unlike the specific values of Γ_1 and Γ_2 of Table 3. The MCDA for each of the 2000 MCS samples is run and the variability of the collected Q_i^+ values is then evaluated. In Figure 11, the variability of the Q_i^+ values is reported in terms of box plots for each of the three candidate solutions over the four considered scenarios (W-W-30, W-W-60, W-WE-30, W-WE-60). As it can be observed, the variability of S5 is almost negligible and its Q_{S5}^+ values are around zero, meaning that S5 is never the near-optimal solution. On the other hand, the variability of the values of Q_{S8}^+ and Q_{S9}^+ has a greater magnitude (e.g., for S8 $\sigma = 0.12, 0.15, 0.15, 0.15$ over the four scenarios, respectively).

Figure 11: Box plots of the values of (a) Q_{S5}^+ , (b) Q_{S8}^+ and (c) Q_{S9}^+ .

Moreover, it is worth analyzing the number of times that each candidate solution is ranked first among the three (i.e., the one with the highest value of Q_i^+ in every MCS). These frequencies are reported in Table 4: it can be seen that S9 is very often the best candidate solution, with S8 being though ranked first in a not negligible number of times (especially for the three last scenarios).

Table 4: Percentage of the times each candidate solution is the near-optimal in the 4 scenarios (with comparison parameters varying in the entire AHP range).

Candidate Solution	Scenario			
	W-W-30	W-W-60	W-WE-30	W-WE-60
S5	0%	0%	0%	0%
S8	5.5%	23.7%	22.4%	23.5%
S9	94.5%	76.3%	77.6%	76.5%

In addition, it is worth evaluating which of the 15 comparison parameters is mostly responsible for the high variability of the Q_i^+ values of S8 and S9. This is done by computing the first order and total Sobol' sensitivity indices. The results for the candidate solution S8 are shown in Figure 12 by means of heat maps to efficiently visualize the sensitivity indices values for each of the four scenarios under study (similar results, not shown in the figure, are obtained for S9). From Figure 12, it emerges that the uncertainty of the first five comparison parameters (i.e., $w_{\beta P}, w_{\beta\eta_1}, w_{\beta\eta_2}, w_{\beta\eta_3}, w_{\beta\eta_4}$) is responsible of almost the whole variability of the Q_i^+ values in each of the four scenarios under study. Moreover, the remaining ten comparison parameters have an almost negligible effect on the variability of the Q_i^+ values, since their total Sobol' sensitivity indices assume values close to zero. This signals that the comparison parameters from $w_{P\eta_1}$ to $w_{\eta_3\eta_4}$ can be set at any given value within their variation range without significantly affecting the variability of the Q_i^+ values. On the other hand, the high values of the first order Sobol' indices for the comparison parameters $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$ reveal that the variability of each

of them is responsible, on average, of almost 20% of the variability of the Q_i^+ values in all the four scenarios. Hence, if the DSO wants to reduce the Q_i^+ variability the most, the best candidates for the title of ‘most influential comparison parameters’ would be $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$. Such information is of considerable help for supporting the algorithm implementation; practically speaking, the DSO deploying the SR algorithm has to consider that the choice of $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$ (i.e., the two comparison parameters among the related criteria) assumes great importance on the decision of the SR solution. Additionally, since the quantity $1 - \sum_i^K S_i$ is around 0.15 in all the four scenarios, the total amount of interactive effects among inputs is a worth 15%.

Figure 12: First order and total Sobol' sensitivity indices for the candidate solution S8.

In view of these results, it is interesting to iterate the whole analysis with the same variability range of all the comparison parameters except $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$, each of which is instead fixed at two specific values, namely $\frac{1}{3}$ and 4 for $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $\frac{1}{2}$ and 5 for $w_{\beta\eta_4}$ (the values already employed for the previous simulations from the Γ_1 and Γ_2 matrices in Table 3). Two distinct situations arise. If $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$ are alternatively fixed at the values of Γ_1 , an overall increase of the times the candidate solution S9 is near-optimal can be highlighted, signaling that $w_{\beta\eta_3} = \frac{1}{3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4} = \frac{1}{2}$ are “adequate” values for S9 to be clearly superior than S8 in being the near-optimal candidate solution. Moreover, the combined effect of simultaneously setting $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$ at the “adequate” values of Γ_1 is higher than fixing them separately and makes S9 be near-optimal in almost 90% of the times, as shown in Table 5. On the other hand, when alternatively fixing $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$ at the values of Γ_2 , a decrease in the number of times that S9 reveals to be near-optimal is observed, with S8 being the near-optimal candidate solution even more often than the situation depicted in Table 4 (i.e., with $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$ left free to vary within their variability range). Also in this case, such tendency is even more stressed when simultaneously setting $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$ at the values of Γ_2 (whose results are shown in Table 6). In practical terms, once SA has allowed to identify which comparison parameters are the most influential ones in affecting the variability of the Q_i^+ — e.g., by analyzing Figure 12—, the final outcome still depends on the specific values assigned to them (here, $w_{\beta\eta_3}$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4}$) for the specific scenario under study. For example, as it is clear from the comparison of Table 4 and 6, choosing a specific value of the most influential comparison parameters might also lead to a less clear distinction among two scenarios in terms of near-optimality, even up to a situation whereby S8 turns to be as near-optimal as S9, e.g., as for the scenarios W-W-60, W-WE-30 and W-WE-60.

Table 5: Percentage of the times each candidate solution is the near-optimal in the 4 scenarios (with $w_{\beta\eta_3} = 0.3$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4} = 0.5$).

Candidate Solution	Scenario			
	W-W-30	W-W-60	W-WE-30	W-WE-60
S5	0%	0%	0%	0%
S8	0.95%	10.5%	9.75%	10.3%
S9	99.05%	89.5%	90.25%	89.7%

Table 6: Percentage of the times each candidate solution is the near-optimal in the 4 scenarios (with $w_{\beta\eta_3} = 4$ and $w_{\beta\eta_4} = 5$).

Candidate Solution	Scenario			
	W-W-30	W-W-60	W-WE-30	W-WE-60
S5	0%	0%	0%	0%
S8	14.85%	50.2%	47.8%	49.8%
S9	85.15%	49.8%	52.2%	50.2%

2.5.3 Modified CIGRE Network without DC sub-network

Further test cases are carried out by excluding the DC sub-network from the modified CIGRE AC-DC test grid. In order to deploy the comparison with the AC-DC test grid used in Section 2.5.1, the DC sub-network is replaced with AC lines and buses having the same network parameters and nominal values of loads and DG. The modified CIGRE AC network is represented in Fig. 13. As in Section 2.5.1, the fault occurrence is considered at bus 3, with the same arrays of prioritized bus groups C_F^{E*} and the candidate solutions in S_{NO} and S_{NO}^{NC} . Moreover, the load and generation profiles shown in Fig. 6 and the AHP comparison parameters of Γ_1 and Γ_2 are used. Fig. 14 shows, for the scenarios S-WE-30 and W-W-15 combined with nominal loads weights at 100% and 120%, the values of the six MCDA criteria for the S_{NO} feasible solutions. With respect to Fig. 8, it can be observed a decrease of the η criteria and an average increase of the power losses (criterion P) in multiple candidate solutions and scenarios. The comparison between each criteria from the tests on AC-DC and AC networks, for every scenarios (season, day of the week and time frame) is performed. The average variations of the criteria values for every candidate solution are reported in Table 7. Only the candidate solutions that are feasible in both tests with AC-DC and DC networks are considered; moreover, since the telecontrolled features of the switches remain unchanged, the analysis focuses only on the criteria P , η_1 , η_2 , η_3 and η_4 . The outcomes show that, on average, the power losses are higher in the AC network than AC-DC one; on the other hand, the η values are higher for the tests in the AC-DC network. Since P is a criterion that aims at being minimized and η are criteria that aim at being maximized, the results indicate, for each criteria, a better performance of AC-DC grid than that of the AC one and, particularly, a better suitability for AC-DC grid in deploying the SR process. The difference among AC-DC and AC grids performances is wider when the nominal load values increase from 100% to 120%.

Table 7: Average variations of criteria values in the candidate solutions among tests on modified CIGRE AC-DC and modified CIGRE AC networks, as absolute values and percentages.

Load	Average variations of criteria values among AC-DC and AC networks									
	P [kW]	P [%]	η_{a1}	η_1 [%]	η_2	η_2 [%]	η_3	η_3 [%]	η_4	η_4 [%]
100%	-8.05	-6.30%	0.16	4.25%	0.21	5.87%	0.12	3.31%	0.40	13.20%
120%	-16.03	-10.72%	0.46	13.20%	0.24	8.08%	0.82	28.59%	0.56	27.41%
Total	-11.72	-8.46%	0.29	8.24%	0.23	7.07%	0.43	14.17%	0.48	19.82%

Figure 13: Modified CIGRE AC Network.

Using the AHP comparison parameters in Γ_1 and Γ_2 , the SR process is deployed and its results are shown in Fig. 15. With respect to the available candidate solutions it is worth to notice that, in the case each sub-array of S_{NO} is discarded due to unfeasibility, no scenario exists in which the candidate solutions of S_{NO}^{NC} are applicable and, in these cases, the near-optimal solution to be implemented belongs to S_{NO-1}^{NC} array; this situation occurs at S-W-30 and W-W-45 for nominal load values at 120%. Moreover, in the same loading condition, for the scenarios with faults occurring at S-WE-45, W-W-75, W-WE-45 and W-WE-75 no feasible SR solution exists. With respect to the results shown from AC-DC grid test in Fig. 9, more scenarios in the AC test grid admits S9 as the only feasible candidate solution. This aspect is in line with the worsening of criteria values shown in Table 7, as the absence of DC sub-networks curtails the power distribution among the two feeders of SS1 and SS2.

2.5.4 Modified MV Oberrhein AC-DC Network

In order to test the scalability of the SR algorithm, assessment tests are conducted on a larger distribution network. The MV Oberrhein network is a generic AC distribution network at 20 kV developed within the Pandapower framework (Thurner et al., 2018). Two HV/MV substations (SS1 and SS2) feed 179 buses grouped in four feeders that are interconnected by six NO tie-switches; the complete network parameters are available in (Fraunhofer IEE and University of

(a) MCDA Criteria at S-WE-30: CIGRE only AC - Load 100%

(b) MCDA Criteria at S-WE-30: CIGRE only AC - Load 120%

(c) MCDA Criteria at W-W-15: CIGRE only AC - Load 100%

(d) MCDA Criteria at W-W-15: CIGRE only AC - Load 120%

Figure 14: MCDA criteria of feasible candidate solutions for modified CIGRE AC network in the scenarios: (a) S-WE-30 with nominal load values at 100%. (b) S-WE-30 with nominal load values at 120%. (c) W-W-15 with nominal load values at 100%. (d) W-W-15 with nominal load values at 120%.

Kassel, 2022). The network has been modified for this work with the addition of a point-to-point DC sub-network, with three DC buses, at 32.6 kV. The modified MV Oberrhein network is represented in Fig. 16, in which the fault occurrence and the tripped switches are highlighted. The network portion bounded by buses 35, 69, 140 and 159 (indicated in Fig. 16) is the area relevant for SR process and is depicted in Fig. 17.

The occurrence of the fault at bus 144 causes the tripping of the upstream switch S4 and, in order to isolate the smallest fault area, the switches S3 and S5 are opened. The array of restorable buses (shown with the yellow circle in Fig. 17) is composed of two sub-arrays, since

Figure 15: MCDA closeness values for modified CIGRE AC network: (a) Γ_1 comparison parameters and nominal load values at 100%. (b) Γ_2 comparison parameters and nominal load values at 100%. (c) Γ_1 comparison parameters and nominal load values at 120%. (d) Γ_2 comparison parameters and nominal load values at 120%.

Figure 16: Modified MV Oberrhein AC-DC network.

these buses must be separately re-energized:

$$C_r = [21, 71, 72, 83, 85, 87, 93, 95, 106, 143, 153], [134, 135, 142, 145]$$

Figure 17: Portion of the modified MV Oberrhein network bounded by buses 35, 69, 140 and 159.

Due to the presence of the NC switch S_2 , the array of restorable bus group is:

$$C_r^g = [[21, 71, 72, 83, 85, 106, 143, 153], [87, 93, 95], [134, 135, 142, 145]]$$

The application of the MCDA technique allows to compute the array of prioritized bus groups:

$$C_r^{g*} = [[87, 93, 95], [134, 135, 142, 145], [21, 71, 72, 83, 85, 106, 143, 153]]$$

Hence, the arrays S_{NO} and S_{NO}^{NC} are calculated, indicating the candidate solutions for the SR being tested:

$$S_{NO} = [[S_1, S_6]]$$

$$S_{NO}^{NC} = [[S_2, S_1, S_6]]$$

It is worth to specify that S_{NO} contains only one sub-array since both NO switches S_1 and S_6 must be closed in order to re-energize every restorable load. Moreover, by applying the sub-array of S_{NO}^{NC} as a candidate solution, the buses included in the last bus group of C_r^{g*} are excluded from the re-energization.

Similarly to Section 2.5.1, the tests are conducted with the load and generation profiles represented in Fig. 6, for the scenarios in each season, day of the week and time frames equal to 15, 30, 45, 60, 75 and 90. The AHP comparison parameters considered in these tests corresponds to Γ_1 . The values of MCDA criteria in the central time frames (30, 60 and 75), for each inspected combination of day and season, are shown in Fig. 18. The different values of criteria η indicate the importance of performing OPF analysis in the future time frames with forecast values, in order to prevent the deployment of SR solutions that become unfeasible before the fault reparation. In the performed tests, the feasibility of S_{NO} candidate solution is verified in each scenario (and, hence, applied as SR solution) except for the scenarios W-W-75 and W-WE-75: in these cases, the candidate solution in S_{NO}^{NC} is tested as feasible and applied as definitive SR solution.

The average computation time for the SR algorithm applied to the modified MV Oberrhein network, measured since the tripping of switches downstream the fault until the issuing of computed switches commands and operating setpoints to the SCADA data bus, corresponds to 15.3 s, having a standard deviation equal to 1.4 s. The data are obtained by repeating 100 times the SR process in the different scenarios. As presented in (Haghgoo, Dognini, & Monti, 2022), in modern DSOs that deploy advanced automated services, the standard duration of

(a) MCDA Criteria at S-W: Oberrhein AC-DC, S1-S6

(b) MCDA Criteria at S-WE: Oberrhein AC-DC, S1-S6

(c) MCDA Criteria at W-W: Oberrhein AC-DC, S1-S6

(d) MCDA Criteria at W-WE: Oberrhein AC-DC, S1-S6

Time Frames:
 — 30
 — 45
 — 60

Figure 18: MCDA criteria of the candidate solution S1-S6 for modified MV Oberrhein AC network in the time frames equal to 30, 45 and 60, in the following scenario: (a) Summer week day. (b) Summer weekend day. (c) Winter week day. (d) Winter weekend day.

FLISR process has an estimation of 5 minutes and the duration of SR itself is evaluated at 3 minutes. Hence the SR algorithm proposed in this work, with respect to the indicated time range, proves to be suitable for a field implementation.

Finally, it is noteworthy that the SR method proposed in this paper showcases a wider degree of applicability as compared to those surveyed in Section 1. In particular the integration of NC switches into the network reconfiguration allows to augment the set of possible candidate solutions. Moreover, considering the MCDA-based prioritization of bus groups to be reconnected offers a way to reflect network criticalities into the SR. Last, the inclusion of load and DG forecasts guarantees a higher robustness of the computed solution, hence alleviating the

DSO burden in the network operations until fault reparation.

2.6 Conclusions

In this chapter the developed SR algorithm for HYPERRIDE project, for the re-energization of AC-DC distribution grids, is presented. The AC-DC grid deploys the interconnection of DC-based loads and generators in the same DC feeders. The field implementation of the proposed algorithm relies on the presence of DC sub-network in the distribution grid as well as the controllability of field devices (AC-DC converters, DG, and switches) with commands and power setpoints via the SCADA system. As opposed to other approaches available in the literature, MCDA has allowed to flexibly combine and objectively prioritize different functional aspects while maintaining their mathematical consistency. The considered features, relevant for the grid operator, are the operational limits in timely modifying the grid topology, the energy efficiency (in relation to the dispatch costs) and the necessary control measures in the hours preceding the fault reparation. The importance of carefully choosing the relative weights of the operational objectives has also been highlighted via SA, which effectively supports the grid operator in tuning the SR in the DMS.

The proposed algorithm has been tested in multiple scenarios, related to different time frames, days of the week and seasons. When more than one candidate solution was feasible (even with differences of the closeness indices down to 5%), the MCDA has resulted crucial to determine the near-optimal one among the re-energization from either the AC-DC converter or an HV-MV substation, hence proving that DC sub-networks expand the set of SR options. As the loads values increased by 20%, the candidate solutions involving just the closing of NO switches have not always guaranteed the respect of operational security limits and, hence, the opening of NC switches was necessary. Additionally, the role of DC sub-networks has proven to be pivotal for the SR: in fact, MCDA criteria showcased an improvement of up to almost 30% when the power injected by AC-DC converters was optimized, determining a higher number of re-energized buses and more feasible SR candidate solutions. This tendency has been revealed to be even more pronounced with higher nominal load values. Moreover, the scalability of the algorithm has been tested in a 182-bus distribution network: the computational time was, on average, 12 times faster than the SR estimated duration, thus being compatible with field deployment requirements.

The described SR algorithm will be implemented, similarly to the other energy services described in this deliverable and part of the HYPERRIDE Task T4.5, in the HYPERRIDE ICT platform (developed in HYPERRIDE WP5) and in the field trials, as the German pilot of HYPERRIDE WP7. In doing so, additional features of the SR algorithm can be modified, in order to keep into considerations the specific field requirements.

3 State Estimation

3.1 Introduction

The operation of electrical power systems is traditionally carried out by system operators in the control centres. The main goal of the operator is to maintain the system in safe conditions, according to the network security constraints, considering the dynamic variations of the power generation and consumption. Additionally, the occurrences of faults cause emergency network conditions that require prompt and effective countermeasures in order to ensure the grid stability. The operation of power networks is becoming more and more complex due to the decentralization of power generation sources. In fact, the whole energy ecosystem is experiencing a massive transformation, moving from the traditional unidirectional power flow (i.e., from few massive power plants to residential or industrial end consumers) to the bi-directional and dynamic (in time and location) power flows. This involves numerous, distributed power generation units (as DER, at customer level) subject to extreme variability. These conditions make the real-time monitoring of power systems more and more complicated and necessary; particularly, in order to carry out the security analysis of the system: the continuous monitoring of the system conditions, the identification of the precise operating state and, eventually, the implementation of the necessary preventive actions (Abur & Exposito, 2004).

Additionally, the information provided by the SCADA system may not always be reliable due to errors in the measurements, telemetry failures, communication noise, etc. Furthermore, the collected set of measurements may not allow direct extraction of the corresponding AC operating state of the system. For instance, bus voltage phase angles are not typically measured, and not all the transmission line flows are available. Besides, it may not be economically feasible to telemeter all possible measurements even if they are available from the transducers at the substations. Moreover, state estimators also function as filters against incorrect measurements, data and other information received through the SCADA system.

The SE allows to identify efficiently and with precision the operational constraints on quantities of the system; it is a mathematical approach applied to power systems and consists of processing redundant measurements in order to provide an optimal estimate of the current operating state. Usually, the states are constituted by voltage phasors at all of the system buses at a given point in time. Consequently, all the other electrical quantities of the network are computed via the fundamental electrotechnical functions. The mathematical technique called WLS is frequently implemented in the state estimation, by integrating the accuracies of measurements and aiming at iteratively minimizing the error of estimated states.

SE was first formulated in 1969 as a WLS problem by Fred Schweppe and his research group (Schweppe & Rom, 1969). Nowadays, state estimators are central parts of every control centre. State estimation has traditionally been applied for the monitoring of transmission systems, gaining more and more attention from the scientific community and grid operators. In recent years, its use is being extended also to distribution grids, considering the necessary adaptations in the algorithms due to, for example, the different sizes of network nodes, the possible phase unbalances, and the reduced availability of measuring devices. Anyway, the expansion to the hybrid AC-DC grids has not reached a maturity level yet: in the dedicated current literature, in fact, only a few research works addressed this specific grid configuration. The critical point is represented by the buses that interface AC and DC systems: the modelling of the power flow values through the AC/DC converter constitutes the difference among the existing methods, in particular with respect to the converter losses. Several approaches rely on successive iterations of a sequential SE algorithm, without considering the converter power losses (Ding,

Chung, & Zhang, 2001; Glover & Sheikoleslami, 1983). On the contrary, the state estimation approach considered in the HYPERRIDE implementation is a two-step technique, developed at the Flexible Electrical Network (FEN) research campus (Forschungs Kampus, 2022) and described in the following sections of this chapter. Within the Task T4.5 of HYPERRIDE project, the algorithm has been implemented as a middleware software component, suitable for the integration as energy service in the ICT HYPERRIDE platform, and tested in multiple loading and measurement scenarios.

3.2 Formulation of AC-DC State Estimation algorithm

The SE method used in this work is the WLS approach (Stengel, 2012), which is based on the minimization of the square of the measurement residual vector, indicated by e_z and satisfying the equation:

$$e_z = z - h(\hat{x}) \quad (52)$$

The measurement residual is the difference between the input measurements z and the measurement function vector $h(\hat{x})$. The measurement function derives the measurement values based on the estimated states \hat{x} . The measurement function is then linearized as:

$$h(\hat{x}) = \mathbf{H}\hat{x} \quad (53)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{H} = \frac{\delta \mathbf{h}(\hat{x})}{\delta \hat{x}} \quad (54)$$

The square of the measurement residual is defined as:

$$J = e_z e_z^T \quad (55)$$

Additionally, each element of the measurement residual $e_{z,[k]}$ is multiplied by a weight, that is defined as the inverse of the input measurement variance. \mathbf{J} is therefore redefined as:

$$\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{e}_z \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{e}_z^T \quad (56)$$

where \mathbf{R} is the measurement covariance matrix, which is a diagonal matrix having as elements the standard deviations of different measurements. Eventually the expression of the state, when the measurement function is linear, is obtained by setting $\frac{\delta J}{\delta \hat{x}} = \mathbf{0}$ in the equation:

$$\hat{x} = (\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{H})^{-1} \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{z} \quad (57)$$

In case the measurement function is non-linear, the state estimates can be calculated via the g Newton-Raphson (NR) iteration defined in the following equation:

$$\hat{x}^g = \hat{x}^{g-1} - (\mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{H})^{-1} \mathbf{H}^T \mathbf{R}^{-1} \mathbf{e}_z^{g-1} \quad (58)$$

For each iteration g of the SE algorithm, the state vector is then updated and the iterative process stops when the given convergence criterion is achieved.

The application of SE to AC-DC grids involves additional requirements that complicate the deployment of the algorithm. Particularly, the AC-DC grid model is divided into three different areas: the AC sub-network, the AC-DC converter station and the the DC sub-network; to deploy

the SE, the synchronisation of states among the three areas and the power balances have to be carried out.

The model of AC-DC converter station is equal to the one explained in Section 2.2.4 of this document, introduced for the OPF of SR algorithm, and shown in Fig. 3. The equations related to power balances on the converter sides, in (15),(16), and the equation expressing the converter current, in (25), are re-used for the deployment of SE algorithm.

The state vector for the AC sub-network, indicated as \mathbf{x}_{AC} , includes voltage magnitudes and phase angles as state variables, yielding to the following state vector:

$$\mathbf{x}_{AC} = [\theta_{AC}, \mathbf{V}_{AC}] = [\theta_2, \dots, \theta_{N_{AC}}, V_1, \dots, V_{N_{AC}}] \quad (59)$$

with N_{AC} as number of nodes in the AC sub-network.

With respect to the DC sub-network the steady state condition is assumed, for which each branch is modelled by a resistive line. Hence the DC state vector \mathbf{x}_{DC} corresponds to the vector of node voltages:

$$\mathbf{x}_{DC} = \mathbf{V}_{DC} = [V_{N_{AC}+1}, \dots, V_{N_{DC}}] \quad (60)$$

with N_{DC} as number of nodes in the DC sub-network.

The activities carried out in the HYPERRIDE project rely on the existing AC-DC SE algorithm developed by RWTH Aachen University and described in (Pau, Sadu, Pillai, Ponci, & Monti, 2016). This algorithm implements WLS method and performs a two-step SE according to the following procedure:

1. The AC and DC sub-networks are separately considered and a state estimation is deployed for each sub-network. AC and DC state estimations rely only on AC and DC measurements (and corresponding uncertainties), respectively.
2. Based on the obtained estimated states, the boundary power at the nodes of converter stations (AC and DC sides) are obtained. Each P_C^{DC} is calculated in two ways:
 - directly from state estimation on DC sub-network,
 - from AC sub-network with (15), starting from P_C^{AC} calculated with AC state estimation and the losses P_C^{loss} computed with (16).

Similarly, Each P_C^{AC} is calculated in two ways:

- directly from state estimation on AC sub-network,
 - from DC sub-network with (15), starting from P_C^{DC} calculated with DC state estimation and the losses P_C^{loss} computed with (16).
3. As second step, the SE is applied again to AC and DC sub-networks independently; in this case, measurements of converter power injection consider the values calculated from the other converter sides (the other sub network):
 - for the AC SE the P_C^{AC} computed by DC sub-network is used.
 - for the DC SE the P_C^{DC} computed by AC sub-network is used.

It is worth to mention that, in order to apply WLS method, in this step the measurements uncertainties of the converter power injections, to build the covariance matrix, are obtained by the inverse of gain matrices.

Additionally, the two-step AC-DC SE algorithm has been enhanced with the improvements described in (Roy, Pau, Ponci, & Monti, 2021). Particularly, the measurements set has been integrated with the control parameter of VSC converters, namely the modulation index m_C according to the following:

$$V_C^{AC} = m_C \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\sqrt{2}} V_C^{DC} \quad (61)$$

The inclusion of this additional measurement allows to increase the performance of the state estimator, taking into account a relevant parameters that is fundamental in the control of AC-DC converter operations. The impact of this measurement in the SE results is shown in the Section 3.3 of this document.

3.3 Test setups for the validation of State Estimation algorithm

The algorithm presented in 3.2, initially available as code in Matlab environment, has been translated to the Python programming language, in order to be properly integrated in the HY-PERRIDE ICT platform and be tested in the projects pilots.

Simulations are performed by considering reference true values and their perturbation according to the assumed measurement uncertainty, in order to obtain the measurement values to be used as input for the SE algorithm. Regarding the measurements uncertainty, all the measurements have been assumed to have uncertainty equal to 2% of the true value, considering Gaussian distributed error and standard deviation equal to one third of this uncertainty. The set on measurement, to which the perturbation is applied, depends on the specific deployed test and includes power, voltage and current measurements on specific nodes.

The SE algorithm is deployed as middleware software component, independent of grid topology, network parameters and measurements set, whose data model is defined according to the structure adopted in the open-source Matlab-based power system simulation package MATPOWER (Zimmerman, Murillo-Sánchez, & Thomas, 2011). The test grid used for the simulations and algorithm validations is the modified CIGRE AC-DC network presented in Section 2.5.1 and shown in Fig. 7, with the same data values. According to the source of true values for the SE, two different test setups are deployed:

- **PYACDCPF test setup** - Power flow simulations were performed with the software PYACDCPF (AAU Energy, 2022), with which the true values are obtained.
- **RTDS test setup** - The modified AC-DC CIGRE network is emulated through the Real Time Digital Simulator (RTDS) with its NovaCor hardware platform (RTDS Technologies Inc., 2023). The RTDS hardware components guarantee the accurate simulation of grid behaviour, allowing to obtain the true values of electrical quantities (to which the random error perturbation is applied, obtaining the measurement values) that are exchanged with the SE algorithm. Grid modelling is carried out via the dedicated software RSCAD: the emulated Remote Terminal Units (RTUs) publish the grid electrical quantities (as reference true values) into the communication network, reaching the interface layer of the platform. In particular, the Gigabit Transceiver Network (GTNET) card of RTDS provides a real-time communication link to and from the simulator via Ethernet. The Fig. 19 and 20 shows the AC and DC sub-networks, respectively, of the modelled modified AC-DC CIGRE network with RSCAD software, whereas Fig. 21 represents the scheme of test setup.

It is worth to mention that, in both the test setups, the obtained true values are perturbed with measurement uncertainties to compute the measurement values. The tests are based on MCS, in the number of 5000 iterations, to assess the statistical evaluations and performances of the proposed estimator.

Figure 19: AC sub-network of the modified CIGRE AC-DC Network modelled in RTDS.

3.4 Test results

In this chapter, a selection of the results obtained by the SE tests with the two presented setups are shown. Multiple tests have involved a variety of measurements to be considered, with different loads profiles and focusing on different electrical quantities (standard deviation, errors, at AC or DC nodes, for voltage magnitudes or voltage angles); hence, the outcomes presented in this document represent just a part of the numerous simulations that have been carried out to validate the SE algorithm.

3.4.1 PYACDCPF test setup: variation of measurement sets

The first tests make use of the power flow simulations with PYACDCPF (hence, without RTDS) to generate the measurement values. Three measurement sets have been deployed and used. The first measurement set "Meas-set-1" includes:

- AC sub-network: voltage magnitude measurements at nodes 1 and 5,

Figure 20: DC sub-network of the modified CIGRE AC-DC Network modelled in RTDS.

Figure 21: RTDS Test Setup for AC-DC State Estimation.

- AC sub-network: active and reactive power flow measurement for each branch,
- DC sub-network: voltage magnitude measurement at node 19,
- DC sub-network: current injection measurement at node 16,
- DC sub-network: current flow measurement for each branch,
- DC sub-network: power injection measurement at node 17.

The second measurement set "Meas-set-2" includes:

- AC sub-network: voltage magnitude measurements at nodes 2, 6 and 12,
- AC sub-network: active and reactive power flow measurement for each branch,
- AC sub-network: active power injection measurements at nodes 5, 6 and 7,
- AC sub-network: reactive power injection measurements at nodes 7, 8 and 9,

- DC sub-network: voltage magnitude measurement at node 19,
- DC sub-network: current flow measurement for each branch,
- DC sub-network: power injection measurements at nodes 17 and 19.

The second measurement set "Meas-set-3" includes:

- AC sub-network: voltage magnitude measurements at nodes 2, 6 and 12,
- AC sub-network: active and reactive power flow measurement for each branch,
- AC sub-network: active power injection measurements at nodes 6, 7 and 8,
- Converter modulation indices at nodes 2, 6 and 12,
- DC sub-network: voltage magnitude measurements at nodes 15, 17 and 20,
- DC sub-network: current flow measurement for each branch,
- DC sub-network: power injection measurements at nodes 17, 19 and 20.

The standard deviation of estimated voltage magnitude at AC nodes, considering the MCS iterations, is reported in Fig. 22, 22 and 22 for measurements sets "Meas-set-1", "Meas-set-2" and "Meas-set-3", respectively. Each figure shows the estimated states after the first SE step (computing AC and DC states separately) and after having completed the second SE step (which has been proposed in (Pau et al., 2016) and described in Section 3.2); the goal of this comparison is to show the impact, on the accuracy of the results, of the second SE step.

Figure 22: Standard deviation of voltage magnitude at AC nodes with "Meas-set-1".

Figure 23: Standard deviation of voltage magnitude at AC nodes with "Meas-set-2".

Figure 24: Standard deviation of voltage magnitude at AC nodes with "Meas-set-3".

Whereas the standard deviation of estimated voltage magnitude at DC nodes is reported in Fig. 25, 26 and 27 for measurements sets "Meas-set-1", "Meas-set-2" and "Meas-set-3", respectively.

Figure 25: Standard deviation of voltage magnitude at DC nodes with "Meas-set-1".

Figure 26: Standard deviation of voltage magnitude at DC nodes with "Meas-set-2".

In all the presented results, the standard deviation remains at small values (between 0.31% and 0.55%), demonstrating the applicability of the algorithm in achieving accurate solutions. The presented outcomes, additionally, show the impact of different measurements sets on the standard deviation of the estimated states: for DC sub-network, "Meas-set-1" and "Meas-set-2" have higher standard deviation than "Meas-set-3"; moreover, the deployment of the second

Figure 27: Standard deviation of voltage magnitude at DC nodes with "Meas-set-3".

estimation step results beneficial in the first two measurements sets. The standard deviation is particularly low, for all inspected cases, in the AC nodes 1 (where the generator and slack bus are located) and 6 (where the AC converter is located, in combination with the measurement of voltage magnitude).

3.4.2 RTDS test setup: variation of load and generation profiles

The results tests deployed with the network modelled and simulated in RTDS, whose setup is shown in Fig. 21, are reported. In these test cases, the measurement set has been kept constant, according to the following:

- AC sub-network: voltage magnitude measurements at nodes 2, 6 and 12,
- AC sub-network: active and reactive power flow measurement for each branch,
- AC sub-network: active power injection measurements at nodes 6, 7 and 8,
- Converter modulation indices at nodes 2, 6 and 12,
- DC sub-network: voltage magnitude measurements at nodes 15, 17 and 20,
- DC sub-network: current flow measurement for each branch,
- DC sub-network: power injection measurements at nodes 17, 19 and 20.

The simulations consider different values of load and generation profiles, according to the Fig. 6 in the configuration (a) "Summer - Week" day. Particularly, the considered time frames are S-W-36, S-W-53 and S-W-72.

The Fig. 28, 29 and 30 show the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) of the voltage magnitudes for AC nodes for time frames S-W-36, S-W-53 and S-W-72, respectively. The same quantities, for the DC nodes, are shown in Fig. 31, 32 and 33.

The RMSE remains at low values for all tested scenarios (in general, below 3%); the highest value is reported, for all the time frames, at node 6 of the AC sub-network (where the AC-DC converter is located). In general, the DC sub-network presents lower values of RMSE (always below 1%). The impact of the second estimator step is different among the nodes of the same sub-networks. It is worth to specify that the RMSE value of the states shall not be directly compared to the perturbation value of the measurements (2% as standard deviation), since they consist of different statistical metrics with a non-linear correlation.

Figure 28: RMSE of voltage magnitude at AC nodes with time frame S-W-36.

Figure 29: RMSE of voltage magnitude at AC nodes with time frame S-W-53.

Figure 30: RMSE of voltage magnitude at AC nodes with time frame S-W-72.

3.4.3 RTDS test setup: impact of measurement of converter modulation index

In order to quantify the impact of the specific VSC converter parameters (in this case, the modulation index of voltages) as measurements for SE, additional tests are performed with RTDS setup. The first measurement set ("Measurement 1") is:

- AC sub-network: voltage magnitude measurements at nodes 2, 6 and 12,
- AC sub-network: active and reactive power flow measurement for each branch,
- AC sub-network: active power injection measurements at nodes 6, 7 and 8,

Figure 31: RMSE of voltage magnitude at DC nodes with time frame S-W-36.

Figure 32: RMSE of voltage magnitude at DC nodes with time frame S-W-53.

Figure 33: RMSE of voltage magnitude at DC nodes with time frame S-W-72.

- Converter modulation indices at nodes 2, 6 and 12,
- DC sub-network: voltage magnitude measurements at nodes 15, 17 and 20,
- DC sub-network: current flow measurement for each branch,
- DC sub-network: power injection measurements at nodes 17, 19 and 20.

The comparison is performed with SE having a second measurement set ("Measurement 2"), equal to the first one but without the values of modulation indices. The tests are performed on the time frames S-W-36 and S-W-53.

The Fig. 34 and 35 show the standard deviation of voltage magnitudes at AC nodes in time

Figure 34: Standard deviation of voltage magnitude at AC nodes with time frame S-W-36.

Figure 35: Standard deviation of voltage magnitude at AC nodes with time frame S-W-53.

Figure 36: Standard deviation of voltage magnitude at DC nodes with time frame S-W-36.

frames S-W-36 and S-W-53, whereas Fig. 36 and 37 show the same quantity at DC nodes. In all the cases, even if small, it is noted the improvement of the results by including the modulation index in the measurement set (in the plots, "Measurement 1").

Finally, the Fig. 38 and 39 show the standard deviation of estimated voltage angles for the nodes of the AC sub-network, which remain at low values (below 0.06%) and confirm the algorithm performance.

Figure 37: Standard deviation of voltage magnitude at DC nodes with time frame S-W-53.

Figure 38: Standard deviation of voltage angle at AC nodes with time frame S-W-36.

Figure 39: Standard deviation of voltage angle at AC nodes with time frame S-W-53.

3.5 Conclusions

This chapter has presented the AC-DC SE that has been implemented in task T4.5 of the HYPERRIDE project. Particularly, the algorithm deploys the WLS approach that includes the accuracies of the measurement devices to perform the computation. Specifically for AC-DC grids, the algorithm makes use of a two-steps approach, which consists of exchanging the estimated values of power flow at the AC-DC converters, and the VSC converter parameters, namely the modulation index to control the voltages at AC and DC sides. The test has been performed by using two different setups for the computation of reference true values: the power flow software PYACDCPF and the RTDS environment. The precision of RTDS simulations allows to perform analysis in conditions closer to the field implementation.

Numerous tests have confirmed the improvement of algorithm performance by using the two-step approach and, additionally, of the measurement set that includes the modulation index. In general, the results proved the suitability of the algorithm in calculating the states (voltage magnitudes and voltage angles, at AC and DC sub-networks), particularly with respect to the standard deviation (based on deployed MCS tests) and RMSE values.

4 Machine Learnt Robust State Estimation and Ideal Measurement Unit Placement

4.1 Introduction

This chapter takes up the subject of state estimation (SE) as discussed in chapter 3 and follows up on it in a more generalised approach and by using machine learning (ML) algorithms as state forecasting tools. The forecasting algorithms are well suited for applications in optimal and real-time control, for grid planning and positioning of measurement units to improve observability. The generalised approach entails that the process here is not limited to predicting the complex phasor voltages at nodes but can be expanded to any quantity of interest in the grid.

ML models can learn arbitrary patterns from data without the requirement of a physical or mathematical model. The learning provides means to automate forecasting and decision-making. Different algorithms exist that provide unique features for a task at hand and many are very fast in doing predictions which makes them ideal candidates for real-time systems. The models are easy to deploy and use in the field, so that a broad spectrum of applications is open to them.

In our previous work ML models were investigated in the context of low-voltage distribution systems. In such systems radial feeder geometries are dominant. This leads to a mostly linear dependence of the voltage magnitudes so that a linear regression (LR) would often suffice to obtain accurate predictions of voltages at unobserved busbars. However, a second algorithm, the artificial neural network (ANN), as a potent algorithm that can embed any non-linear behaviour was employed too and yielded equal results.

The developed machine learnt approach for distribution system state estimation does not rely on any historical measurement data or pseudo-measurements. The only input required is the grid topology. Combined with a power flow solver a training dataset can be retrieved so that enough training data will always be accessible to generate, which avoids the often encountered lack-of-data issue in ML applications.

In the course of task 4.5 of the project two novel topics of machine learnt state estimation were investigated:

- if the approach is feasible also in a hybrid AC/DC grid of medium voltage with low observability and
- if machine learning models for state estimation can be made robust to noisy or wrong data.

4.2 Problem formulation

Machine learning methods for state estimation in hybrid AC/DC grids are not well researched yet. So far the topology-based approach has only been used in the low-voltage power distribution system. In this work, the approach was applied to a medium-voltage hybrid AC/DC grid for the first time. For consistency the same grid as above in chapter 3 was chosen. We investigated scenarios of placements of measurement devices in the grid to achieve different grades of observability and gain insights on the most ideal placement of the devices.

In the topology based approach the training dataset, consisting of the results of the power flow

solver, may be artificial compared to real measurement values from meters in the grid. These have a certain level of noise from various origins and measurement inaccuracies, which could lead to a data shift between training and application in a real world system. ML models are known to be sensitive to deviations in the data. This applies not only to data shifts between training and production stage but also to measurement noise, failures of measurement devices or attacks where wrong data is injected. It is a well-known fact that many ML projects fail in the deployment/production stage due to problems with datasets and model training that cause data cascades, which frequently prevent successful model deployment (Sambasivan et al., 2021).

Efforts have been taken to find means to make models more accurate and robust, including strategies like data augmentation, where a limited set of training data is inflated with suitable methods, and adversarial model training, where potential data attacks are accounted for in the model design process (Jagielski et al., 2018; Nakamura & Fukagata, 2022; Shorten & Khoshgoftaar, 2019).

Here, we exposed models to three different kinds of noisy, augmented or adverse data under the premise to obtain more robust ML models for regression tasks:

Poisoning the training data with Gaussian noise: A Gaussian distribution provides a simple noise model, easy to implement and widely used in the electric power system literature. It is assumed to be the dominant part in the noise so that traditional state estimation techniques as formulated in chapter 3 can be applied. For this work the standard specification accuracy classes for electricity meters were used as orientation for the upper bound of the noise level of measurement devices, with a maximum allowed value of 2% (Cetina, Roscoe, & Wright, 2017). The noise then follows the well-known distribution

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp -\frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}, \quad (62)$$

around the mean value μ and with spread given by the standard deviation σ .

Monte Carlo sampling of poisoned data points with Gaussian noise: The concept of data augmentation was established in image recognition to improve classification outcomes with limited amounts of sample data the model could be exposed to. This limitation led to overfitting. In data augmentation the sample is modified to create a new instance for model training (Shorten & Khoshgoftaar, 2019). The question was raised if in the regression problem at hand, the ANN could also benefit from oversampling training instances to create multiple training instances per power flow result but with different noise values. Due to the Gaussian nature of the noise used in these Monte Carlo samples it was not expected to make any difference for the LR model.

Poisoning the training data with noise following a Gaussian mixture model: In reality noise profiles in the electric power system could be non-Gaussian (Nakamura & Fukagata, 2022; Huang et al., 2021) so that this should be accounted for when selecting and training ML algorithms. Therefore, a Gaussian mixture model (GMM) was employed to cover this behaviour. A GMM is defined by the function

$$g(x) = \sum_{m=1}^M \alpha_m f(x; \mu_m, \sigma_m), \quad (63)$$

with mixing proportions α_m that follow $\sum_M \alpha_m = 1$ and Gaussian densities f (Hastie, Tibshirani, Friedman, & Friedman, 2009). With a GMM noise sources like wrong device calibrations or faulty devices that produce shifted or outlier data can be simulated.

The following research questions were posed:

- Does the ML approach originally developed for distribution grids work in a MV hybrid AC/DC network and what are the achievable accuracies for different algorithms?
- How low can the observability of a system be to still reach an acceptable accuracy level for SE? Where should measurement devices be placed for maximum system information gain?
- ML models per default are sensitive to noise in the data, can models be made robust?

4.3 Machine learnt robust SE methods

4.3.1 Model training method

ML Algorithms

Approaches employing ML are increasingly common tools in power systems research and applications, since they are able to learn patterns from data without explicit programming. Important aspects are the choice of an adequate training dataset, algorithms and training parameters to reach a good prediction accuracy. The chosen algorithms for the SE task at hand were twofold: an artificial neural network and a linear regression model. The LR model has the advantages of its ease of use and transparency of parameters, however, the ANN can capture non-linearities in the regression problem, if present, and achieves a more versatile model, due to its many trainable internal parameters. On the other hand, ANNs are usually very sensitive to data shifts.

Grid specifications

As mentioned above, the same grid as in chapter 3 was employed, a modified AC-DC CIGRE network, as shown in the AC and DC sub-networks of figures 19 and 20. However, the exact specification of components like the AC-DC converters and the switching states may slightly deviate.

Training data generation

Input requirements for the model training were aimed to be kept very low so that here, only the grid topology is required. Historical datasets or pseudo-measurements, as commonly used in other machine learning approaches, are not used. In fact, the often encountered lack of training data is a non-issue in this case since the dataset is generated from the topology information with a suitable power flow solver, ideally including losses at the converters in the AC-DC grid.

Scenarios

Each model was trained specifically for a certain scenario, where a scenario in this context is a given amount of known and unknown quantities in the grid, with the positions of the known and unknown quantities topologically clearly defined. Quantities used in training and prediction were combinations of the AC and DC voltages at certain busbars and the active and reactive powers of corresponding loads. The scenarios were created randomly with varying fractions of known quantities of a type n_q in the grid, with the fraction defined as,

$$f_q = \frac{n_q}{N_q}, \quad (64)$$

and N_q the total amount of quantities of type q , with q e.g. the voltage magnitudes at busbars. Five scenarios per fraction of known voltages at the busbars were created, in total 95.

For each scenario, multiple shallow feed-forward ANNs and a single LR model were trained, in the case of the ANNs with hyperparameter-tuning and cross-validation for the selection of the best-performing model. Inputs to the models were the scenario-dependent known voltages and loads while the unknown voltage magnitudes were the prediction outputs. It had been previously established in another project that the additional knowledge of load information improved the prediction accuracy of the voltage forecast for the unobserved positions in the grid.

4.3.2 Adverse and augmented datasets

As mentioned above in section 4.2 three different approaches were investigated to improve model robustness to adverse conditions like noise in data or measurement outliers:

1. Poisoning the training data with Gaussian noise
2. Monte Carlo sampling of poisoned data points with Gaussian noise
3. Poisoning the training data with noise following a Gaussian mixture model

Additionally, a choice was made to either use the adverse samples only for the model inputs (features) or for the model in- and outputs (features and labels). For comparison and to determine the idealised case metrics, 'vanilla' models were trained on the unpoisoned but highly artificial training dataset for the different scenarios.

Vanilla dataset

Power flow results were calculated for 87600 samples of loads combinations originating from uniform distributions of active and reactive powers in the system, with bounds of -0.5 and +0.5 MW for the active powers and for the reactive powers as a random uniform distribution of up to 10% the corresponding active power, as shown in fig. 40a). For that the commercial software PowerFactory was used in a quasi-dynamic simulation.

Gaussian adverse 2% and adverse 4% datasets

Gaussian noise was randomly sampled from a distribution with mean the idealised values given by the power flow result in the vanilla dataset and standard deviation as a tuneable parameter. It was set to either 2% or 4% of the mean as the 3σ interval of the distribution. The standard deviation percentage was the same for all the voltage magnitudes and loads in the two datasets. The residuals of the 2% dataset compared to the original power flow results are plotted as a histogram in Fig. 40b).

Monte Carlo sampled adverse dataset

In this case, before creating the Gaussian adverse samples as described in the paragraph above the power flow results for each record in the dataset were copied four times so that multiple adverse examples with different Gaussian noise per record resulted.

Gaussian mixture model adverse dataset

The Gaussian mixture model consisted of three parts visualised in Fig. 41: 60% of the data as base measurement noise equal to the Gaussian adverse 2% dataset with distribution symmetric around the values of the power flow dataset, 30% as a shifted Gaussian adverse 2% part with mean at a 5% increased value from the power flow dataset - resembling a wrongly calibrated measurement device and 10% outliers as a widespread Gaussian distribution with mean at a

Figure 40: a) Load active and reactive power distributions used in all the datasets. b) Residuals of Gaussian adverse 2% dataset and the original power flow values. In the 2% and 4% datasets only a single adverse sample was created per record as indicated by the red dot. In the Monte Carlo sampled adverse dataset four samples were generated per record as indicated by the grey dots.

Figure 41: Gaussian mixture model residuals showing the three parts: 60% original Gaussian adverse data with 2% spreading, a portion of 30% shifted with a bias and a portion of 10% shifted and spread out to resemble outliers.

20% increased value from the power flow data. It is pointed out that the total error distribution in this case is not symmetric any more.

4.3.3 Metrics

Models were evaluated and benchmarked against each other with a test dataset that was not used in the training. For the evaluation, two metrics were chosen that complement each other well - the root mean square error (RMSE),

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i^p - y_i^o)^2}, \quad (65)$$

with y_i^p , y_i^o the predicted value, observed value at i respectively, and the coefficient of determination (R^2),

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SSQ_{res}}{SSQ_{tot}}, \quad (66)$$

with SSQ_{tot} the total sum of squares, SSQ_{res} the residual sum of squares and yielding values from -inf to 1 (good fit).

The *RMSE* penalises outliers more strongly than for example the mean absolute error and has the unit of the estimated quantity. The R^2 value is a score for the 'goodness' of a fit. Together both give a good impression of the overall performance, since a low *RMSE* value is not necessarily a good fit (low R^2) but likewise a high R^2 (perfect fit) may not have any real significance concerning the error, for example if the variance of data points is generally very low.

4.4 Results and discussion

In the following, the obtained results to the posed research questions in relation to machine learnt robust SE are being presented and discussed.

4.4.1 Prediction accuracy of state estimation from observability-scenarios for the MV hybrid AC/DC grid topology

To look into this problem the 'vanilla' training dataset was used and evaluated for each of the five randomly created scenarios of measurement positions per fraction of observed voltage magnitudes in the grid.

A known or observed quantity was defined as a quantity that was measured in the grid. Metrics M_i^q of a quantity q at position i in the grid were aggregated within the individual scenario as

$$M_{avg}^{sc} = \frac{1}{\bar{n}_q} \sum_i M_i^q, \quad (67)$$

with \bar{n}_q the number of predicted quantities in the scenario.

In general the $RMSE_{avg}^{sc}$ for the unobserved voltages in the AC part of the grid was below 0.001 p.u. for most fractions, only if the fraction of known voltages was equal to or below 14% did the average error increase in some of the scenarios to about 0.007 p.u. (fig. 42 left side). ANN and LR performed equally well as seen in the figure by the mostly overlapping dots, so that it can be concluded that the problem is mostly linear. The DC part of the grid featured only tiny fluctuations in the DC voltages so that the LR model fits better than the ANN but the metric's differences only have a limited amount of significance here (fig. 42 right side).

The interplay of accuracy and observability in the AC part of the grid is directly visible from fig 42. For very good observability of the grid (i.e., the fraction of knowns is close to one), the error becomes very low and the R_{avg}^{2sc} score close to one signals a very good prediction. With decreasing observed locations in the grid the metrics fortunately stay well for quite a period and only at low fractions start to deteriorate significantly. A similar behaviour was encountered in previous studies in various low-voltage grids.

Figure 42: Averaged metrics per random scenario for the unobserved voltages in the AC (left) and DC (right) part of the modified Cigre grid for the ANN and LR algorithms. Upper graphs show the $R^2_{sc_{avg}}$ metrics, lower ones the $RMSE_{sc_{avg}}$ in p.u. values. Each dot corresponds to a single scenario defined by the fraction of known voltage magnitudes at busbars and their corresponding loads (x-scale).

Figure 43: Decreased performance of models trained on the 'vanilla' dataset when exposed to a dataset with 2% Gaussian noise.

4.4.2 Robust state estimation in the observability-scenarios

The exposed 'vanilla' case

In the next step, the above discussed models trained on the 'vanilla' dataset were exposed to noisy, and therefore more realistic data, in the form of the 2% and 4% Gaussian adverse datasets. The effects are discussed in relation to the AC part of the grid but were similar for the DC side nevertheless. In most cases a more than ten-fold increase in the $RMSE_{sc_{avg}}$ on the AC side was the consequence, especially for the ANN, while the DC part performed metrics-wise even worse (fig. 43). This highlights that the choice of the dataset used in training is crucial for ANN models to perform well outside of an artificial laboratory environment. Due to the Gaussian nature of the noise the LR still performed in the limit set by the noise.

Figure 44: Performance of models trained on the Gaussian adverse 2% dataset. In case 1 on the left, only the features were poisoned with noise but the labels were taken from the 'vanilla' dataset, while in case 2 on the right features and labels were poisoned with noise.

Figure 45: Performance of models trained on the Gaussian adverse 2% dataset if tested on the Gaussian 4% data. In case 1 on the left only the features were poisoned with noise but the labels were taken from the 'vanilla' dataset, while in case 2 on the right features and labels were poisoned with noise.

Training on Gaussian adverse 2% dataset

Models were trained on the Gaussian adverse 2% dataset and their performance was compared with the previous results. Two different cases were investigated: in the first only the features were poisoned with noise but the labels were taken from the 'vanilla' dataset (case 1), while in the second features and labels were poisoned (case 2).

It can be taken from figure 44 that the $RMSE_{avg}^{SC}$ has increased but only moderately for the first case with ANN and LR now performing equally again. In the second case, the two algorithms performed as expected from the noise limitation. Both cases show that while the LR on Gaussian data is robust, the ANN can be made robust by exposing it to adverse samples in the training.

Testing models trained on the 2% adverse data with 4% adverse data

The use of a test dataset with a high standard deviation does not increase the error as strongly as seen before. As shown in Fig. 45 the ANN model, therefore, has become robust against Gaussian error distributions.

Monte Carlo sampled adverse dataset

It was investigated if a Monte Carlo sampled dataset could reduce the error in the Gaussian

Figure 46: $R^2_{sc_{avg}}$ and $RMSE_{sc_{avg}}$ in p.u. values for the models trained on the Gaussian mixture model dataset. The noise here is non-symmetric of shape shown in Fig. 41.

noise 2% and 4% cases. This appears not to be the case. The additional training instances of the four-fold increased dataset did not give an advantage in model performance. Since with the proposed SE method enough training data can always be generated Monte Carlo sampling will not be required.

Gaussian mixture model adverse dataset

In this situation the noise on the power flow data was non-symmetrically distributed as given by the discussed GMM. Training and testing the algorithms on this dataset shows worse metrics for the LR model, while the ANN can learn to handle the non-linearity in the dataset (fig. 46).

4.5 Conclusions

In this chapter, a novel approach to state estimation employing machine learning and only requiring the topology information of the grid was applied to a MV hybrid AC/DC network for the first time. It was investigated how measurement positioning influences the prediction performance of the models and what the dependence is on the number of measurement devices, especially for low observability scenarios. It was found that the method performs very well even in scenarios with few observed positions in the grid. The findings confirm previous results established for low-voltage distribution grids.

Furthermore, it was investigated how robust the two chosen algorithms were to adverse noise in the training and testing data and if models could be made robust. It can be concluded that linear regression is robust on Gaussian (symmetric) data while artificial neural networks are robust on data that was similar to training data and can have a non-Gaussian non-linear distribution. This demonstrates that the ANN can be made robust to new types of data if exposed to it in the training process. If Gaussian noise was encountered then the discussed case 2 is the most realistic real scenario with both algorithms performing equally well. If the noise is non-Gaussian the ANN was the preferable option.

5 Conclusions

This document has presented the energy services specifically designed for the monitoring and control of AC-DC distribution grids. The first algorithm corresponds to a SR algorithm based on MCDA for the restoration of de-energized nodes, following a fault occurrence, which accounts for forecasts of loads and generation as well as the number and type of operated switches. The algorithm has proved the role of AC-DC converters and DC sub-networks as support to deploy SR: the performances have increased in case the control of AC-DC converters, based on a convexified, OPF have been included. The second algorithm consists of a two-step AC-DC SE, which employs the data exchange among AC and DC sub-networks (regarding power flow in the AC-DC converters) to improve the grid estimation; its implementation in RTDS setup allowed to test the dynamic behaviour of the power grid in different conditions.

A novel approach to state estimation employing machine learning and only requiring the topology information of the grid was applied to an MV hybrid AC-DC network. Even in low observability settings, the prediction performance was high for both of the two used algorithms. It was found that the artificial neural network algorithm could be made robust to various types of noise if exposed to it in training and that the linear regression model was confirmed robust to symmetrically distributed noise. The results demonstrate the feasibility of the topology based approach to deploy machine learnt predictors outside of laboratory conditions.

The scalability of the proposed algorithms has been partially addressed, particularly for the SR by applying the algorithm on the large Oberrhein distribution grids with 400 nodes. Anyway, to entirely verify the suitability of each proposed algorithm (SR and every SE methods) on distribution networks with very high amount of nodes, additional scalability tests are necessary and will be included in the future works; the algorithms may need specific technical adaptation as the distribution of algorithm execution as Multi-Agent System (MAS).

The proposed energy services expand the knowledge about operations and applicability of AC-DC distribution grids, providing tested solutions that are ready to be implemented in the pilot activities. In the following step, the energy services will be integrated into the HYPER-RIDE ICT platform, in order to provide references and specifications for the tests in the project pilots.

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